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**Quantum Treatment of Simple Molecular Ions:
Predissociation and Photodissociation
of $(\text{Ne-H})^+$ and $(\text{Ar-H})^+$**

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In addition to the thesis, candidates prepare two supplementary short theses (“*tesine*”) based on scientific articles, one of which is randomly selected and presented during the final defense.

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*To my family,
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Abstract

Simple molecular ions such as those studied in this work represent, beyond being an interesting molecular system in their own right, a topic of growing relevance in plasma physics and in particular in nuclear fusion research, where knowledge of how noble gases interact with charged particles is essential. The study of molecular ions such as $(\text{He-H})^+$, $(\text{Ne-H})^+$, $(\text{Ar-H})^+$ provides precise information on this type of interaction and also represents a first step towards the study of ionic clusters of the form $(\text{R-H})_n^+$, where R denotes a noble gas atom, which form in plasma-matter interactions and whose dissociation mechanisms are of considerable interest.

The determination of the interaction potential for such systems using both dynamical data (differential cross sections) and spectroscopic data represents a necessary step towards a complete treatment of the R-H^+ interaction that takes seriously into account the long-range part governed by mutual polarisation forces, which is essential for describing bulk properties such as the diffusion coefficient and the mobility of charged particles in noble gases.

The $(\text{He-H})^+$ system is the simplest among these to study: having only two nuclei and two electrons, accurate ab-initio calculations describing its properties have been carried out, and from the experimental side it is the most thoroughly investigated, with its resonant states having been observed via predissociation and photodissociation.

As one moves down the noble gas column of the periodic table, the R-H^+ interaction becomes progressively stronger, the depth of the potential well increases, and the growing richness of bound and resonant states makes a description in terms of a simple intermolecular potential, as defined within the Born-Oppenheimer approximation in which the entire work is carried out, increasingly demanding.

The mathematical tools used in this thesis to solve the equation for the nuclear degrees of freedom consist of two programs, one for bound states and one for continuum states, both of which use the Numerov propagator to generate the solutions.

The work first attempts, using a method based on a perturbative calculation, to derive the form of the potential directly from the energies of the bound states;

through several examples the unreliability of some simple intermolecular potentials currently in use for describing the R-H⁺ interaction is demonstrated, while the flexibility of the so-called “modified potentials”, obtained from the analysis of various properties of the systems, is highlighted.

A critical survey of several “modified” intermolecular potentials proposed in the literature and derived from dynamical data is then presented; bound state energies, transitions, and differential cross sections are computed and compared with experimental data in order to optimise the potentials. Estimates of the energies and widths of the resonances of both (Ne-H)⁺ and (Ar-H)⁺ are then carried out for the first time, using both semiclassical boundary-condition methods, which reduce the computation of resonances to a level of difficulty comparable to that of bound states, and exact quantum mechanical calculations of partial scattering cross sections; the two methods are shown to be practically equivalent.

Finally, by studying the photodissociation cross section in the vicinity of the resonance energies, it is shown that the presence of the electromagnetic field driving the discrete → continuum transition does not appreciably alter the position of the resonance, so that photodissociation occurs at final-state energies consistent with those found by the other methods. Using the formula derived in the theory of the anisotropy parameter, it is further shown that photodissociation can exhibit a rapid transition to a highly anisotropic fragment distribution at energies close to the resonance energies.

Atomic Units

ATOMIC UNITS: with the abbreviation “a.u.” the following units of measurement for electric charge, length, mass and energy are defined as:

mass	1 a.u. = m_e	= 9.109534×10^{-28} g
length	1 a.u. = $a_o = \hbar^2/m_e e^2$	= 0.52917706 Å
energy	1 a.u. = $e^2/a_o = m_e e^4/\hbar^2$	= $4.3598125 \times 10^{-11}$ erg
electric charge	1 a.u. = e	= 4.803242×10^{-10} u.e.s.

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Chapter I

Introduction

The study of the interaction between a noble gas atom and a proton will be carried out in this thesis within the framework of the Born-Oppenheimer approximation (Born '27), whose derivation and limits of validity are outlined below in brief and qualitative form.

The complete eigenvalue problem for a diatomic molecule is represented by the equation:

$$[K_e(r) + K_n(R_1, R_2) + V(r, R_1, R_2)]\Psi(r, R_1, R_2) = E \Psi(r, R_1, R_2) \quad (\text{I.1})$$

where $K_e = -(\hbar^2/2m_e) \sum_i \Delta_i$ and $K_N = -\hbar^2(\Delta_1/2M_1 + \Delta_2/2M_2)$ are the kinetic energy operators for the electrons and the nuclei respectively; $V(r, R_1, R_2)$ is the total interaction potential of the nuclei and electrons; r represents the set of electron coordinates r_1, r_2, \dots, r_N , while R_1 and R_2 represent the coordinates of the two nuclei.

Since in the molecular centre-of-mass reference frame the magnitudes of the momenta P_e and P_N of the electrons and nuclei are of the same order of magnitude, $P_e \cong P_N \cong P$ (in terms of spatial coordinates this is equivalent to saying that the wave function will vary, as the electron coordinates change, at the same rate as it does with respect to changes in the nuclear coordinates), and therefore so will their squares, the kinetic energy of the nuclei, $K_N \cong P^2/2M$, will be approximately m_e/M times smaller than the kinetic energy of the electrons, $K_e \cong P^2/2m_e$ (where M and m_e represent an average nuclear mass and the electron mass respectively).

One therefore first solves an equation in which the nuclear kinetic terms are neglected, the “fixed-nucleus equation”:

$$[K_e(r) + V(r, R_1, R_2)]\Phi(r; R_1, R_2) = W(R_1, R_2) \Phi(r; R_1, R_2) \quad (\text{I.2})$$

which describes the motion of the electrons around the nuclei held fixed at positions R_1, R_2 . Solving this equation yields the electronic wave functions $\Phi(r; R_1, R_2)$ and the corresponding eigenvalues $W(R_1, R_2)$ depending parametrically on the nuclear configuration R_1, R_2 at which equation (I.2) has been solved. The eigenvalue $W(R)$, which by the symmetry of the system around the internuclear axis depends only on $R = |R_1 - R_2|$, is then used in an equation for the nuclei alone with the interaction potential:

$$[K_n(R_1, R_2) + W(R)]\Psi(R_1, R_2) = E\Psi(R_1, R_2) \quad (\text{I.3})$$

The total wave function constructed as follows:

$$F(r, R_1, R_2) = \Phi(r; R_1, R_2)\Psi(R_1, R_2) \quad (\text{I.4})$$

together with the eigenvalues E , differs from the exact solution of equation (I.1) by terms smaller by a factor of approximately m_e/M (Born '27, Landau Ch. XI, Slater Ch. XIX).

Equation (I.3), once the motion of the centre of mass $R_b = (M_1R_1 + M_2R_2)/(M_1 + M_2)$ has been explicitly separated from the relative motion $R = R_2 - R_1$, and the solution $\Psi(R, \Theta)$ expanded in Legendre polynomials, $\Psi(R, \Theta) = \sum_J P_J(\cos \Theta) \times \Psi_J(R)$, can be written, for a single partial solution $\Psi_J(R)$, as:

$$[P_R^2 + W(R) + J(J+1)\hbar^2/2MR^2]\Psi_J(R) = E\Psi_J(R) \quad (\text{I.5})$$

where $P_R = -i\hbar R^{-1}\partial_R R$ is the radial momentum operator.

Although $W(R)$ represents the effective interaction potential between the two nuclei of the molecule, its more general significance becomes apparent when one considers that, given the large mass of the nuclei relative to that of the electrons, the position of the centre of mass of each nucleus and its mass correspond approximately to those of the corresponding atom; $W(R)$ then represents the interaction potential between the two atoms, and we shall henceforth refer to it as the "intermolecular potential". Equation (I.5) can thus be regarded as an equation for the atoms treated as interacting particles with an effective potential $W(R)$; if the two atoms of the molecule are identical, $W(R)$ represents the interaction potential between atoms of the corresponding gas or liquid, as commonly used in statistical mechanics.

This circumstance will allow us to treat collisions between a noble gas atom and a proton using the same potential $W(R)$ with which we shall study their bound states.

A simple interpretation of why $W(R)$, obtained as an eigenvalue of equation (I.2), can be used as the interaction potential in equation (I.3), is provided by the Hellmann-

Feynman theorem (Feynman '39): multiplying equation (I.2) by $\Phi^*(r; R_1, R_2)$ and integrating over all electron coordinates one obtains:

$$W(R) = \int \Phi^*(r; R_1, R_2) [K_e(r) + V(r, R_1, R_2)] \Phi(r; R_1, r_2) dr \quad (\text{I.6})$$

If $W(R)$ represents the ‘‘classical interaction potential’’ for the two nuclei, such that its use as the interaction potential in an eigenvalue equation for the nuclei alone provides a correct description of their quantum behaviour, then its derivative with respect to R_1 , for example, should give the force F_1 acting on nucleus 1. Setting $H_e = K_e + V$ one has:

$$\begin{aligned} -F_1 = \partial W(R)/\partial R_1 &= \int (\partial \Phi^*/\partial R_1) H_e \Phi + \int \Phi^* (\partial H_e/\partial R_1) \Phi + \int \Phi^* H_e (\partial \Phi/\partial R_1) \\ &= W(R) \left[\int (\partial \Phi^*/\partial R_1) \Phi + \int \Phi^* (\partial \Phi/\partial R_1) \right] + \int \Phi^* (\partial H_e/\partial R_1) \Phi \end{aligned} \quad (\text{I.7})$$

Since the expression in square brackets is simply $\partial/\partial R_1 \int (\Phi^* \Phi) dr = 0$, and since K_e does not depend on the nuclear coordinates, one obtains:

$$F_1 = -\partial W(R)/\partial R_1 = \int dr |\Phi|^2 (-\partial V/\partial R_1) = \langle -\partial V/\partial R_1 \rangle \quad (\text{I.8})$$

Taking as the explicit expression for $V(r, R_1, R_2)$ the electrostatic potential of nuclei and electrons:

$$V(r, R_1, R_2) = Z_1 Z_2 e^2 / R - \sum_i [Z_1 e^2 / |R_1 - r_i| + Z_2 e^2 / |R_2 - r_i|] \quad (\text{I.9})$$

and denoting by ρ_e the electron density:

$$\rho_e(x) = e \sum_i \int dr_1 \cdots dr_{i-1} dr_{i+1} \cdots dr_n \cdot |\Phi(r_1, \dots, r_{i-1}, x, r_{i+1}, \dots; R_1, R_2)|^2 \quad (\text{I.10})$$

one finally obtains:

$$F_1 = (Z_1 Z_2 e^2)(R_1 - R_2)/|R_1 - R_2|^3 - \int dx \rho_e(x) Z_1 e (R_1 - x)/|R_1 - x|^3 \quad (\text{I.11})$$

which is simply the electrostatic force experienced by nucleus 1 due to the presence of nucleus 2 and the molecular electron cloud with charge density $-e\rho_e(x)$.

The eigenvalue $W(R)$ therefore represents, under the assumption made in equation (I.9) for $V(r, R_1, R_2)$, the electrostatic interaction potential between the nuclei and the electron cloud in the configuration corresponding to internuclear distance R ;

and the electrostatic interaction represents the dominant contribution to the total interaction, especially when one of the two atoms is ionised, as in the case of the molecular ions we are about to study.

* * *

The study of protonated noble gases $(R-H)^+$, where R will henceforth denote one of the noble gas atoms, will begin directly from equation (I.3) for the nuclei alone, bypassing equation (I.2); that is, we will seek the intermolecular potential $W(R)$ directly, and will restrict attention to that corresponding to the ground electronic state, $^1\Sigma^+$, in which the electrons have zero total orbital angular momentum around the internuclear axis, $\Lambda = 0$, and zero total spin, $S = 0$. For this state, information derived from various types of experiment is available and described in greater detail later:

- measurements of the energies of the lowest bound states of $(Ne-H)^+$, $(Ne-D)^+$, $(Ar-H)^+$ and $(Ar-D)^+$ from Penning ionisation experiments;
- spectroscopic transitions between different rovibrational states of $(Ar-H)^+$, $(Ne-H)^+$ and several other isotopologues;
- differential cross sections, measured at various energies, for scattering between protons and neon, argon, and krypton;
- measurements of the mobility and diffusion coefficient for $(Ne-H)^+$.

Experiments concerning the $(He-H)^+$ system have not been mentioned, since an accurate potential (Kolos '76, Bishop '79) and theoretical studies of its resonances (Peek '73) and photodissociation (Atabek '85 A,B) are already available for that system. For $(Kr-H)^+$, one would need Penning ionisation data for krypton, which are not yet available; without them an accurate estimate of the potential well depth, and hence of the positions and widths of the resonances, is not possible. The study of $(Xe-H)^+$, on the other hand, would necessarily require consideration of at least the first three potential curves corresponding to the first three electronic states of $(Xe-H)^+$, since the curves of the first two excited electronic states, which correspond to asymptotic states $Xe^+ + H$, are repulsive and cross the ground-state curve at a few atomic units before tending to asymptotic limits corresponding to energies lower than that of the ground-state asymptotic limit, which we take as the zero of energy (Sidis '73); the description of $(Xe-H)^+$ would therefore also involve the phenomenon of spontaneous predissociation due to the crossing of the electronic curves. For these reasons we shall concentrate our attention on the $(Ar-H)^+$ and $(Ne-H)^+$ systems.

All the information needed for comparison with experimental data is derivable from the intermolecular potential $W(R)$ and depends in an essential way on its form; the primary task is therefore to find potentials that satisfactorily reproduce the experimental data, with an accuracy that cannot be much less than that associated with the Born-Oppenheimer approximation itself, of order $m_e/M \cong 0.4\%$, since otherwise it would be smaller than the precision with which the intermolecular potential itself is defined.

The theory and mathematical tools that will be used to solve the Schrödinger equation for the nuclei alone, derived within the Born-Oppenheimer approximation, and to make predictions and comparisons with experiments, are described in Chapter II.

Chapter III contains a description of the potentials obtained by inversion of the collision data and a verification of their quality through the calculation and comparison of bound states and elastic differential cross sections.

Chapter IV finally examines the processes involving continuum states, considering transitions to resonant levels and the decay of predissociating resonant states. For these processes the energies and widths of the resonant states are calculated, as well as the behaviour of the partial scattering and photodissociation cross sections in the vicinity of the resonance energies.

Chapter II

Quantum Treatments and Computational Methods

CHAPTER II-1 :

THE CALCULATION OF BOUND STATES

§1 : Propagation of the solution

The method used (Le Roy '86) to solve the bound-state problem is, briefly, the following: the Schrödinger equation is replaced by a finite-difference equation derived with the Numerov method, which, being employed by all the programs used in the present work, is described in a separate section (see the Appendix to Chapter II) for greater clarity.

The equation is integrated numerically between two limits R_{\min} and R_{\max} , with $R_{\min} > 0$ and R_{\max} finite. To obtain an accurate solution it is necessary to choose R_{\min} sufficiently smaller than the first turning point R_A corresponding to the energy of the highest eigenvalue for which the equation is to be solved (see Figure (II-1)), and analogously R_{\max} sufficiently larger than the second turning point R_B ; the number of integration steps must be large enough to ensure that there are at least twenty steps between one node of the wave function and the next.

To start the calculation, estimates of the wave function are first made at two pairs of points: two points at $R = R_{\min}$ and $R = R_{\min} + \Delta$, and two more at $R = R_{\max}$ and $R = R_{\max} - \Delta$, where Δ is the integration step.

For the first pair of points one simply sets $\psi_1(R_{\min}) = 0$ and $\psi_1(R_{\min} + \Delta) = 1$, since $\Psi(R \rightarrow 0) = 0$ and $\Psi'(R \rightarrow 0)$ is not known. For the second pair of points one takes $\psi_2(R_{\max}) = 1$ and $\psi_2(R_{\max} - \Delta)$ from the JWKB semiclassical formula for the

wave function:

$$\psi(R) \propto [E - W(R)]^{-1/4} \exp \left[\int dR \sqrt{2M(E - W(R))/\hbar^2} \right] \quad (\text{II 1.1})$$

normalised so that $\psi_2(R_{\max}) = 1$.

The two wave functions $\psi_1(R)$ and $\psi_2(R)$, illustrated in Figure (II-2), after taking an estimate E for the eigenvalue, are propagated with the Numerov method to a midpoint C , chosen as the point at which $\psi_1(R)$ presents its first maximum, where, with an appropriate rescaling, one can arrange that $\psi_1(C) = \psi_2(C)$.

INTEGRAZIONE NUMERICA NELLA RICERCA DEGLI STATI LEGATI.

Fig. II-1 and Fig. II-2 — Numerical integration in the search for bound states: integration limits R_{\min} , R_A , R_B , R_{\max} and matching of the wave functions ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 at the point C .

This method does not naturally yield the solution at the first attempt, since at the matching point the logarithmic derivative of the wave function will not be continuous unless the energy E used coincides with one of the eigenvalues; many attempts, and hence many propagations of the solutions over a number of integration steps of the order of several thousand, would be required to obtain an accurate solution.

§2 : Search for eigenvalues

There exist, however, methods that allow one to estimate the correction ΔE that must be added to the initially chosen value E in order to obtain the nearest eigenvalue $E + \Delta E$. The method presented below allows the eigenvalues to be found with great accuracy in only 3 or 4 iterations each (Smith Ch. 14); it determines ΔE from knowledge of the (uncorrected) function $\psi(R)$, which according to the above is equal to:

$$\psi(R) = \psi_1(R) \equiv \chi_1(R)/R \quad \text{for } R < C \quad (\text{II 1.2a})$$

$$= \psi_2(R) \equiv \chi_2(R)/R \quad \text{for } R > C \quad (\text{II 1.2b})$$

We note that the functions χ_1 and χ_2 , although not representing an exact solution, satisfy for $R < C$ and $R > C$ respectively the following equations (by virtue of having been propagated as prescribed by the differential equation):

$$\left[d^2/dR^2 + U(R) + E - J(J+1)/R^2 \right] \chi_i = 0 \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (\text{II 1.3})$$

where for brevity of notation we have set $E = (2M/\hbar^2) \times (\text{EIGENVALUE})$ and $U(R) = 2MW(R)/\hbar^2$. We now seek the value ΔE such that $E + \Delta E$ is the correct eigenvalue, and denote by $\chi_i + \Delta\chi_i$ the corresponding exact eigenfunction:

$$\left[d^2/dR^2 + U(R) + (E + \Delta E) - J(J+1)/R^2 \right] (\chi_i + \Delta\chi_i) = 0 \quad (\text{II 1.4})$$

Taking into account equations (II 1.3) and neglecting the term proportional to $\Delta\chi \times \Delta E$ one obtains:

$$\left[d^2/dR^2 + U(R) + E - J(J+1)/R^2 \right] \Delta\chi_i = -\Delta E \times \chi_i \quad (\text{II 1.5})$$

Multiplying equation (II 1.3) by $\Delta\chi_i$ and (II 1.5) by χ_i and taking the difference, one obtains:

$$\chi_i'' \Delta\chi_i - \chi_i \Delta\chi_i'' \equiv d/dR [\chi_i' \Delta\chi_i - \chi_i \Delta\chi_i'] = -\Delta E \times \chi_i^2 \quad (\text{II 1.6})$$

We now integrate the equation with $i = 1$ from $R = 0$ to $R = C$, and the equation with $i = 2$ from $R = C$ to $R = \infty$, obtaining:

$$\Delta E \int_0^C \chi_1^2 dR = [\chi_1' \Delta \chi_1 - \chi_1 \Delta \chi_1']_0^C \equiv [-\chi_1^2 \Delta(\chi_1'/\chi_1)]_0^C \quad (\text{II 1.7a})$$

$$\Delta E \int_C^\infty \chi_2^2 dR = [\chi_2' \Delta \chi_2 - \chi_2 \Delta \chi_2']_C^\infty \equiv [-\chi_2^2 \Delta(\chi_2'/\chi_2)]_C^\infty \quad (\text{II 1.7b})$$

For $i = 1$ it can be shown that at $R = 0$ both χ_1 and $\Delta \chi_1$ (since the limit of the wave function as $R \rightarrow 0$ is known) vanish; analogously for $i = 2$ at $R = \infty$ both χ_2 and $\Delta \chi_2$ vanish (the latter because the JWKB behaviour of the wave function is known for sufficiently large R); denoting by χ_c the common value that χ_1 and χ_2 take at $R = C$, one then has:

$$\Delta E \int_0^C \chi_1^2 dR = -\chi_c^2 \Delta[\chi_1'/\chi_1]_C \quad (\text{II 1.8a})$$

$$\Delta E \int_C^\infty \chi_2^2 dR = +\chi_c^2 \Delta[\chi_2'/\chi_2]_C \quad (\text{II 1.8b})$$

Adding these two equations one obtains:

$$\Delta E \int_0^\infty \chi^2 dR / \chi_c^2 = \Delta[\chi_2'/\chi_2]_C - \Delta[\chi_1'/\chi_1]_C \quad (\text{II 1.9})$$

We now note that the expressions in square brackets are simply the logarithmic derivatives of χ_i at $R = C$; since $\chi_i + \Delta \chi_i$ is the exact solution, its logarithmic derivative will be continuous, in particular at $R = C$:

$$\chi_1'(C)/\chi_1(C) + \Delta[\chi_1'/\chi_1]_C = \chi_2'(C)/\chi_2(C) + \Delta[\chi_2'/\chi_2]_C \quad (\text{II 1.10})$$

Substituting equation (II 1.9) into (II 1.10) one finally obtains:

$$\Delta E = \chi_c [\chi_1'(C) - \chi_2'(C)] / \int_0^\infty |\chi(R)|^2 dR \quad (\text{II 1.11})$$

which represents the estimated correction to be applied to E .

Setting $E \rightarrow E + \Delta E$, the calculation of the solution is iterated until ΔE is smaller than the required precision.

CHAPTER II-2 : THE CALCULATION OF CONTINUUM STATES

One speaks of elastic scattering either when two structureless bodies collide, or when two bodies collide under conditions such that their internal state is not modified during the collision.

In our case the internal state is represented by the electronic structure, which does not appear in the study of the interaction of single atoms via the Born-Oppenheimer equation for the nuclei, in which the atoms are formally treated as elementary particles interacting through a potential $W(R)$.

As long as we restrict ourselves to considering a single electronic state (the ground state) and to studying scattering phenomena in which no change of electronic state occurs, the internal structure of the colliding atoms will remain unchanged and the scattering will therefore be elastic.

This situation will remain valid in the range of energies to be considered in the scattering of protons by noble gases ($E < 30$ eV), since these energies will not be sufficient to induce transitions between different electronic states, and all exit channels corresponding to electronic states other than the ground state will therefore be closed.

* * *

§1 : Formulation of the quantum problem

We now turn to the quantum mechanical treatment of the problem (Schiff Ch. V, Landau Ch. XVII), through the equation:

$$\left[-(\hbar^2/2M)\Delta + W(R) \right] \Psi(R, \Theta) = E \Psi(R, \Theta) \quad (\text{II } 2.1)$$

where, assuming the limit $W(R \rightarrow 0)$ to be zero, E is positive; it formally represents the problem of scattering of a particle of mass $M = M_1 M_2 / (M_1 + M_2)$ from a fixed centre, with which it interacts through the potential $W(R)$ depending only on the distance of the particle from the scattering centre.

The characteristics of the scattering are determined by the wave function in the region far from the scattering centre, where measurements are performed, that is by its asymptotic limit as $R \rightarrow \infty$.

Assuming, as in the one-dimensional scattering case, that this asymptotic form is a linear combination of a part representing the incident wave and a part representing

the scattered wave, one must verify that, since the scattering is elastic, both the incident wave, which we take to travel along the Z axis, and the scattered wave, in whatever direction it has been scattered, are eigenfunctions of the momentum operator with the same eigenvalue.

Since the eigenfunction of the momentum operator along the Z axis, $-i\hbar\partial_z$, is proportional to $\exp(ikz)$, and since the eigenfunction of the radial component of the momentum operator, $-i\hbar R^{-1}\partial_R R$, is proportional to $\exp(ikR)/R$, the asymptotic form of the wave function will be, apart from a multiplicative factor:

$$\Psi(R \rightarrow \infty) = e^{ikZ} + f(\Theta) e^{ikR}/R \quad (\text{II } 2.2)$$

$f(\Theta)$ represents the angular dependence of the scattered wave which, by the symmetry of the interaction around the Z axis, depends not on the angle φ but only on Θ (the scattering angle in the centre-of-mass reference frame).

The first term of equation (II 2.2), which strictly speaking represents an infinite plane wave whose presence would give rise to interference phenomena with the scattered wave at any scattering angle, is included in order to correctly represent the contribution of the incident wave to the asymptotic wave function; it should be understood as a wave limited by the slits which in the experimental apparatus restrict the transverse dimensions of the incident beam. These dimensions are large enough to allow diffraction effects to be neglected (much larger than the wavelength of the incident beam), and to treat the incident wave as plane, but small enough compared with the dimensions of the experimental apparatus (much smaller than the product $R \times \tan(\Theta)$) so that no interference between the scattered and incident waves occurs, except at very small angles (see Figure (II-3)).

SCHEMA DI UN 'ESPERIENZA DI DIFFUSIONE.

FIGURA II-3

Fig. II-3 — Schematic diagram of a scattering experiment.

Therefore when calculating the current density of the scattered wave via the formula:

$$J = (\hbar/2iM)[\Psi^*\nabla\Psi - (\nabla\Psi^*)\Psi] \quad (\text{II } 2.3)$$

one must use, for Ψ , only the asymptotic part $f(\Theta)\exp(ikR)/R$, thereby avoiding interference terms with the incident wave; substituting into equation (II 2.3) one obtains:

$$J = (\hbar k/M)|f(\Theta)|^2\mathbf{r}/|R|^2 = v|f(\Theta)|^2\mathbf{r}/|R|^2 \quad (\text{II } 2.4)$$

where \mathbf{r} is the radial unit vector and $v = \hbar k/m$ is the velocity of the projectile. The number of projectiles $dN/d\Omega$ emerging per unit solid angle per unit time is then given by:

$$dN/d\Omega = (J \cdot \mathbf{r})R^2 = v|f(\Theta)|^2 \quad (\text{II } 2.5)$$

We note that v is precisely the magnitude of the current density J_{inc} of the incident wave e^{ikz} as defined in equation (II 2.2), as can be verified by substituting $\Psi = \exp(ikz)$ into equation (II 2.3) for the current density.

Comparing relation (II 2.5) with the relation:

$$dN/d\Omega = J_{inc}(d\sigma/d\Omega) \quad (\text{II } 2.6)$$

which defines the differential cross section for a single scattering centre, one concludes that:

$$d\sigma/d\Omega = |f(\Theta)|^2 \quad (\text{II } 2.7)$$

The total cross section is then:

$$\sigma = 2\pi \int |f(\Theta)|^2 d(\cos \Theta) \quad (\text{II } 2.8)$$

It thus follows that all information about the scattering is contained in $f(\Theta)$. An analytical expression for it can sometimes be found by solving equation (II 2.1) with the partial-wave method (used here), which we now proceed to describe.

§2 : Partial wave analysis

In the continuum case as well, the solution of equation (II 2.1), $\Psi(R, \Theta)$, can be expanded in Legendre polynomials $P_K(\cos \Theta)$: $\Psi(R, \Theta) = \sum_K A_K \Psi_K(R) P_K(\cos \Theta)$. Multiplying the equation by $P_J(\cos \Theta)$ and integrating over the angle one obtains the equation for the radial function of a single ‘‘partial wave’’ with orbital angular momentum J :

$$\left[-(\hbar^2/2M)R^{-1}(\partial_R)^2 R + J(J+1)\hbar^2/2MR^2 + W(R) \right] \Psi_J(R) = E \Psi_J(R) \quad (\text{II } 2.9)$$

Setting $k = \sqrt{2ME/\hbar^2}$, $X = kR$, equation (II 2.9) can be rewritten as:

$$\Psi_J'' + (2/X)\Psi_J' + \left[1 - J(J+1)/X^2 \right] \Psi_J - (2M/\hbar^2 k^2) W(R) \Psi_J = 0 \quad (\text{II } 2.10)$$

For $W(R) \equiv 0$, i.e. in the case of a free particle, equation (II 2.10) becomes:

$$\Psi_J''(X) + (2/X)\Psi_J'(X) + [1 - J(J+1)/X^2]\Psi_J(X) = 0 \quad (\text{II 2.11})$$

which, with the substitution $\Psi_J = \varphi_J/\sqrt{X}$, transforms into the Bessel equation of order $L = J + 1/2$:

$$\varphi_J'' + (2/X)\varphi_J + [1 - (J + 1/2)^2/X^2]\varphi_J = 0 \quad (\text{II 2.12})$$

whose solution is a linear combination of the Bessel and Neumann functions J_L and N_L ; the solution of equation (II 2.11) is therefore represented by a linear combination of the spherical functions:

$$j_J(kR) = J_{J+1/2}(kR)\sqrt{\pi/2kR} \quad (\text{II 2.13a})$$

$$n_J(kR) = N_{J+1/2}(kR)\sqrt{\pi/2kR} \quad (\text{II 2.13b})$$

The solution of the free-particle equation must however be finite at the origin, and this requirement is satisfied only by the spherical Bessel function j_J , which is thus the solution.

The asymptotic limits of the two functions (II 2.13) are:

$$j_J(kR \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow \{\cos[kR - (J + 1)\pi/2]\}/kR \quad (\text{II 2.14a})$$

$$n_J(kR \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow \{\sin[kR - (J + 1)\pi/2]\}/kR \quad (\text{II 2.14b})$$

The asymptotic limit of the free-particle wave is therefore:

$$\Psi_J^\circ(kR) = [\sin(kR - J\pi/2)]/kR \quad (\text{II 2.15})$$

Regarding the asymptotic limit of equation (II 2.10), we note that if as $R \rightarrow \infty$, $W(R) \rightarrow 0$ faster than $1/R^2$, it reduces to equation (II 2.11) for a free particle.

As described in greater detail in the introduction to Chapter III, the ion-atom potential reduces at large distances to the polarisation potential $-\alpha e^2/2R^4$ (α is the atomic polarisability) and indeed decreases faster than $1/R^2$.

The solution in the asymptotic region can therefore be expressed as a combination of the spherical functions (II 2.13):

$$\Psi_J(kR) = \alpha_J j_J(kR) + \beta_J n_J(kR) \quad (\text{II 2.16})$$

where α_J and β_J are constants on which no restriction need be imposed, unlike the

free-particle case; without loss of generality we set:

$$\alpha_J = B_J \cos \delta_J \quad (\text{II 2.17})$$

$$\beta_J = -B_J \sin \delta_J \quad (\text{II 2.18})$$

and the asymptotic limit of equation (II 2.16), using equations (II 2.14), can be written as:

$$\Psi_J(kR) = -B_J[\sin(kR - J\pi/2 + \delta_J)]/kR \quad (\text{II 2.19})$$

The only difference between this expression and expression (II 2.15) for the asymptotic limit of a free particle is the phase shift δ_J , which can thus be obtained by direct comparison between the wave function solving equation (II 2.10) in the asymptotic region and the function of equation (II 2.15).

We now illustrate the relation between the phase shifts δ_J and the differential cross section $d\sigma(\Omega)/d\Omega = |f(\Theta)|^2$.

To this end we take the limit $R \rightarrow \infty$ of the partial-wave expansion of the solution:

$$\Psi_J(kR \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow \sum_J A_J P_J(\cos \Theta) [\sin(kR - J\pi/2 + \delta_J)]/kR \quad (\text{II 2.20})$$

This function must coincide with the asymptotic form introduced in equation (II 2.2), so one must have:

$$e^{ikZ} + f(\Theta) e^{ikR}/R = \sum_J A_J P_J(\cos \Theta) [\sin(kR - J\pi/2 + \delta_J)]/kR \quad (\text{II 2.21})$$

From this equation it is now possible to derive an expression for $f(\Theta)$ in terms of the phase shifts, and thereby solve the theoretical problem of elastic scattering.

Setting, without loss of generality:

$$f(\Theta) = (1/2ik) \sum_J (2J + 1) f_J P_J(\cos \Theta) \quad (\text{II 2.22})$$

and using the asymptotic Legendre expansion of $\exp(ikZ) = \exp(ikR \cos \Theta)$:

$$e^{ikZ} = \sum_J (i)^J (2J + 1) P_J(\cos \Theta) j_J(kR) \quad (\text{II.1})$$

$$\rightarrow \sum_J (i)^J (2J + 1) P_J(\cos \Theta) [\sin(kR - J\pi/2)]/kR \quad (\text{II 2.23})$$

equation (II 2.21) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} & (1/kR) \sum_J (2J+1) P_J(\cos \Theta) [(i)^J \sin(kR - J\pi/2) + e^{ikR} f_J/2i] = \\ & = (1/kR) \sum_J \Lambda_J \sin(kR - J\pi/2 + \delta_J) P_J(\cos \Theta) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{II 2.24})$$

Given the orthogonality of the Legendre polynomials ($\int P_J(\cos \Theta) P_K(\cos \Theta) d(\cos \Theta) = 0$ if $K \neq J$), equation (II 2.24) is equivalent to a series of equations, one for each value of J :

$$(2J+1)(i)^J \sin(kR - J\pi/2) + (2J+1)f_J e^{ikR}/2i = \Lambda_J \sin(kR - J\pi/2 + \delta_J) \quad (\text{II 2.25})$$

This equation is in turn equivalent to two equations, one for each of the two independent functions $\exp(ikR)$ and $\exp(-ikR)$, which can be obtained by expanding the sine in complex exponentials and comparing the coefficients of $\exp(\pm ikR)$ on the left and right sides:

$$\Lambda_J = (i)^J (2J+1) \exp(i\delta_J) \quad (\text{II 2.26a})$$

$$f_J = \Lambda_J (-i)^J \exp(i\delta_J) / (2J+1) - 1 = \exp(2i\delta_J) - 1 \quad (\text{II 2.26b})$$

The amplitude $f(\Theta)$ can therefore be written as:

$$f(\Theta) = (1/2ik) \sum_J (2J+1) P_J(\cos \Theta) [\exp(2i\delta_J) - 1] \quad (\text{II 2.27})$$

and the differential cross section as:

$$d\sigma(\Omega)/d\Omega = (1/4k^2) \left| \sum_J (2J+1) P_J(\cos \Theta) [\exp(2i\delta_J) - 1] \right|^2 \quad (\text{II 2.28})$$

The total cross section is finally:

$$\sigma = \int d\Omega (d\sigma/d\Omega) = (4\pi/k^2) \sum_J (2J+1) |\sin(\delta_J)|^2 = \sum_J \sigma_J \quad (\text{II 2.29})$$

where σ_J represents the ‘‘partial cross section’’:

$$\sigma_J = (4\pi/k^2) (2J+1) |\sin(\delta_J)|^2 \quad (\text{II 2.20})$$

The partial cross section σ_J reaches a maximum of $4\pi(2J+1)/k^2$; in this case its value is 4 times larger than what one might expect from semiclassical arguments

(Weisskopf Ch. VIII) in which a partial wave is treated as a cylindrical wave of radius b given by:

$$(bk)^2 = J(J + 1) \tag{II 2.31}$$

Taking the difference between (II 2.31) and the analogous expression written for $(J - 1)$ one obtains:

$$k^2 \Delta(b^2) = 2J \tag{II 2.32}$$

The area of the annular ring of wave J is approximately given by (see Figure (II-4)):

$$S \cong \pi \Delta(b^2) \tag{II 2.33}$$

Taking from equation (II 2.32) the expression for $\Delta(b^2)$ one obtains:

$$S \cong (\pi/k^2)(2J) \cong \sigma_J/4 \tag{II 2.34}$$

* * *

FIGURA II-4

Fig. II-4 — Semiclassical representation of the partial cross section σ_J .

§3 : Numerical integration

The numerical program used here repeatedly solves equation (II 2.9) for a single partial wave for different values of J ranging from $J = 0$ to a certain J_{\max} .

The solution is propagated with the Numerov method (see the Appendix to Chapter II) from $R = R_{\min}$, which lies at small values of R in the classically forbidden region, up to $R = R_{\max}$ where the potential has become negligible, where the phase shifts δ_J are determined.

The potential $W(R)$, at small distances, will for the most part represent the electrostatic repulsion between two nuclei and will therefore not grow faster than $1/R$, becoming negligible compared with $J(J+1)/2MR^2$; the wave function at small values of R will then satisfy the equation:

$$[R\Psi_J(R)]'' = [J(J+1)/R^2]R\Psi_J(R) \quad (\text{II } 2.35)$$

whose solution, finite at the origin, is proportional to:

$$\Psi_J(R) \propto R^J \quad (\text{II } 2.36)$$

which is taken as the initial form at $R \cong R_{\min}$.

At large distances, in order to maintain greater accuracy, one does not perform the comparison between the asymptotic forms of the wave function in the presence of the potential and the free-particle wave function, $\sin(kR - J\pi/2 + \delta_J)$ and $\sin(kR - J\pi/2)$ to be precise, but instead uses equation (II 2.16) directly; the point at which the potential begins to be negligible is indeed reached before the point at which the asymptotic expressions (II 2.14) begin to be good approximations to the Bessel and Neumann functions.

Taking the logarithmic derivative with respect to R of expression (II 2.16), one has:

$$\Psi_J^{\infty'}(kR)/\Psi_J^{\infty}(kR) = k [j_J'(kR) \cos \delta_J - n_J'(kR) \sin \delta_J] / [j_J(kR) \cos \delta_J - n_J(kR) \sin \delta_J] \quad (\text{II } 2.37)$$

This expression is evaluated numerically at $R = R_{\max}$ where it is expected to be well satisfied; denoting by γ_J the value of the logarithmic derivative at $R = R_{\max}$:

$$\gamma_J = \Psi_J^{\infty'}(kR_{\max})/\Psi_J^{\infty}(kR_{\max}) \quad (\text{II } 2.38)$$

the phase shift δ_J can be determined from the relation:

$$k [j_J'(kR_{\max}) \cos \delta_J - n_J'(kR_{\max}) \sin \delta_J] / [j_J(kR_{\max}) \cos \delta_J - n_J(kR_{\max}) \sin \delta_J] = \gamma_J/k \quad (\text{II } 2.39)$$

Dividing both numerator and denominator of the left-hand side by $\cos \delta_J$ and isolating $\tan \delta_J$ one finally obtains:

$$\tan(\delta_J) = [kj_J'(kR_{\max}) - \gamma_J j_J(kR_{\max})] / [kn_J'(kR_{\max}) - \gamma_J n_J(kR_{\max})] \quad (\text{II } 2.40)$$

The functions j_J , n_J , j_J' , n_J' are computed analytically by the program using dedi-

cated subroutines, while γ_J is computed numerically from the wave function via (II 2.38).

Once the phase shifts are known, the differential cross section is calculated with formula (II 2.28) written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 d\sigma(\Omega)/d\Omega &= (1/4k^2) \left| \sum_J (2J+1) P_J(\cos \Theta) [\exp(2i\delta_J) - 1] \right|^2 \\
 &= (1/4k^2) \left\{ \left[\sum_J (2J+1) P_J(\cos \Theta) [\cos(2\delta_J) - 1] \right]^2 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \left[\sum_J (2J+1) P_J(\cos \Theta) \sin(2\delta_J) \right]^2 \right\} \quad (\text{II 2.41})
 \end{aligned}$$

We observe that although the relation:

$$\sum_J (2J+1) P_J(\cos \Theta) = 0 \quad \text{for } \Theta \neq 0 \quad (\text{II 2.42})$$

might appear to simplify the expressions for the differential cross section, it must not be used in a numerical calculation where the sums are performed over a finite number of partial waves, in which case relation (II 2.42) does not hold. The factor (-1) appearing in $f(\Theta)$ represents the contribution of the incident amplitude and must be retained; this is clear by observing that as $J \rightarrow \infty$, $\delta_J \rightarrow 0$ and the expressions $(\sin \delta_J)$ and $(\cos \delta_J - 1)$ present in $d\sigma/d\Omega$ tend to zero, but not $(\sin \delta_J)$ and $(\cos \delta_J)$.

The value J_{\max} of the maximum partial wave included was determined by incrementing it until the cross section was insensitive to further increases in J_{\max} .

The critical value at which the calculations, for the potentials used, appeared to converge is $J_{\max} \cong 1000$; we note that this value is of the order of magnitude of the value estimated semiclassically from the relation:

$$\sqrt{[J(J+1)]} \cong J \cong bk = b\sqrt{(2ME)} \quad \text{with } b, M, E \text{ in a.u.} \quad (\text{II 2.43})$$

where setting the reduced mass $M \cong 1822 m_e$, $E \cong 1$ a.u., $b \cong 10$ a.u. as an estimate of the largest impact parameter at which a particle is appreciably deflected, one obtains $J_{\max} \cong 600$.

The effect of using too small a J_{\max} manifests itself in the cross section in the manner shown in Figure (II-5), where examples of cross sections for $(\text{Ne-H})^+$ calculated for different values of J_{\max} are compared.

* * *

FIG. II-5

Fig. II-5 — Cross sections with different numbers of partial waves: comparison for 1000, 800 and 400 partial waves.

§4 : Transformations between reference frames

The expressions obtained so far for the differential cross section are valid in the centre-of-mass reference frame, where Θ represents the scattering angle and E the relative kinetic energy.

Many experiments, however, directly report the counts of scattered particles as a function of the laboratory scattering angle Θ_{lab} at a given energy E_{lab} of the proton beam incident on the noble gas sample, which is at rest in the laboratory.

Before making comparisons, the necessary transformations must therefore be performed, whose form is readily derived from the conservation laws of the reaction (Schiff Ch. V).

If, as in Figure (II-6), we denote by V_b the velocity of the centre of mass, by $V_{1\text{lab}}$ the velocity that the projectile of mass M_1 has in the laboratory reference frame after the collision, and by $V_{1\text{cm}}$ the same velocity in the centre-of-mass reference frame, the comparison of the X and Y components of the projectile momentum in the two reference frames is written as:

$$X: \quad V_{1\text{cm}} \cos(\Theta) + V_b = V_{1\text{lab}} \cos(\Theta_{\text{lab}}) \quad (\text{II } 2.44\text{a})$$

$$Y: \quad V_{1\text{cm}} \sin(\Theta) = V_{1\text{lab}} \sin(\Theta_{\text{lab}}) \quad (\text{II } 2.44\text{b})$$

from which, eliminating $V_{1\text{lab}}$:

$$\tan(\Theta_{\text{lab}}) = \sin(\Theta) / [\cos(\Theta) + V_b/V_{1\text{cm}}] \quad (\text{II } 2.45)$$

The velocity $V_{1\text{cm}}$ of the projectile in the centre-of-mass frame is:

$$V_{1\text{cm}} = M_2 V / (M_1 + M_2) \quad (\text{II } 2.46)$$

where V is the relative velocity. The velocity of the centre of mass in the laboratory reference frame is instead given by:

CONFRONTO TRA IL SISTEMA DI RIFERIMENTO DEL LABORATORIO
E IL SISTEMA DI RIFERIMENTO DEL CENTRO DI MASSA.

FIGURA II-6

Fig. II-6 — Comparison between the Laboratory reference frame and the Centre-of-Mass reference frame.

$$V_b = M_1 V_{in} / (M_1 + M_2) = M_1 V / (M_1 + M_2) \quad (\text{II } 2.47)$$

where V_{in} is the initial velocity of the projectile in the laboratory frame, which coincides with the relative velocity.

The ratio $\gamma = V_b / V_{1cm}$ is therefore M_1 / M_2 and the relation between the angles

Θ and Θ_{lab} of equation (II 2.45) becomes:

$$\tan \Theta_{\text{lab}} = \sin(\Theta)/[\gamma + \cos(\Theta)] = \sin(\Theta)/[M_1/M_2 + \cos(\Theta)] \quad (\text{II 2.48})$$

where M_1 is the mass of the projectile and M_2 that of the target.

The total cross section is an invariant, and the differential cross section transforms as follows:

$$d\sigma/d\Omega_{\text{lab}} = d\sigma/d\Omega_{\text{cm}}(d\Omega_{\text{cm}}/d\Omega_{\text{lab}}) = (d\sigma/d\Omega_{\text{cm}})|d \cos \Theta/d \cos \Theta_{\text{lab}}| \quad (\text{II 2.49})$$

provided it does not depend on the angle φ . From equation (II 2.48) we obtain:

$$\cos(\Theta_{\text{lab}}) = 1/\sqrt{(1 + \tan^2 \Theta_{\text{lab}})} = (\gamma + \cos \Theta)/\sqrt{[1 + 2\gamma \cos \Theta + \gamma^2]} \quad (\text{II 2.50})$$

and after differentiating with respect to $\cos(\Theta)$ we obtain the transformation formula for the differential cross section:

$$d\sigma/d\Omega_{\text{lab}} = d\sigma/d\Omega_{\text{cm}} [1+2\gamma \cos \Theta + \gamma^2]^{3/2} / |1+\gamma \cos \Theta| \quad \text{with } \gamma = M_1/M_2 \quad (\text{II 2.51})$$

It remains to derive the form of the energy transformation.

If we denote by E the relative kinetic energy in the centre-of-mass reference frame, on passing to the laboratory reference frame it transforms to:

$$E_{\text{lab}} = E + (M_1 + M_2)V_b^2/2 \quad (\text{II 2.52})$$

expressing the centre-of-mass velocity V_b according to equation (II 2.47) one obtains:

$$E_{\text{lab}} = E + [M_1/(M_1 + M_2)]E_{\text{lab}} \quad (\text{II 2.53})$$

where $M_1 V_b^2/2 = E_{\text{lab}}$ has been set. One finally obtains the relation between E and E_{lab} :

$$E = [M_2/(M_1 + M_2)]E_{\text{lab}} \quad (\text{II 2.54})$$

to be used to estimate the energy E at which to calculate the cross section in the centre-of-mass frame for an incident beam energy E_{lab} in the laboratory frame. We summarise the formulae to be used for transforming the various quantities between the two reference frames:

CENTRE OF MASS \rightarrow LABORATORY	
Θ	$\rightarrow \Theta_{\text{lab}} = \arctan[\sin \Theta / (\gamma + \cos \Theta)]$ with $\gamma = M_1/M_2$ (II 2.55a)
$d\sigma(\Theta)/d\Omega$	$\rightarrow d\sigma(\Theta_{\text{lab}})/d\Omega_{\text{lab}} = [d\sigma(\Theta)/d\Omega][1 + 2\gamma \cos \Theta + \gamma^2]^{3/2}/ 1 + \gamma \cos \Theta $, where Θ_{lab} is given by transformation (II 2.55a). (II 2.55b)
E	$\rightarrow E_{\text{lab}} = (1 + M_1/M_2)E$ (II 2.55c)

§5 : Semiclassical description of scattering

We wish now to describe some general characteristics of the differential cross section for an intermolecular potential of the form used in the study of protonated noble gases (Child Ch. , Pauly '79), qualitatively illustrated in Figure (II-7), where the potential is schematically divided into the “repulsive part”, the “well”, the attractive region around $R = R_e$, and the tail of the potential, arising from the polarisation interaction between the two atoms.

It is worthwhile considering the classical motion of a particle moving in the potential of Figure (II-7). After the interaction with the scattering centre the particle appears deflected by the scattering angle Θ , which is shown in Figure (II-8) as a function of the impact parameter b together with a graphical representation of some classical trajectories.

The analytical dependence of Θ on the impact parameter b is:

$$\Theta(b) = \pi - 2 \int_r^\infty dR (bP/R^2) / \sqrt{[2M(E - W(R)) - b^2P^2/R^2]} \quad (\text{II 2.56})$$

where P is the momentum of the incident particle and r is the root of the equation:

$$2M[E - W(r)] - b^2P^2/r^2 = 0 \quad (\text{II 2.57})$$

and therefore represents the radial turning distance.

As appears in Figure (II-8), $\Theta(b) \cong \pi$ for small values of b ; as the impact parameter is increased the deflection angle decreases to a minimum value $\Theta_{\text{min}} = -\Theta_R$, then increases and tends to zero as $b \rightarrow \infty$.

We note, however, that although it is theoretically possible to speak of positive or negative scattering angles Θ (corresponding respectively to an effective repulsion or attraction of the particle by the potential), it is operationally impossible to distinguish the sign of Θ , which we shall conventionally assume to lie between 0 and π : $0 < \Theta < \pi$.

To correctly represent the deflection function we therefore plot $|\Theta(b)|$, obtaining the graph shown in Figure (II-9). It is now apparent that there are three values of the impact parameter, b_1 , b_2 and b_3 , that give rise to scattering at the same angle Θ_0 , and this occurs for every $\Theta_0 < \Theta_R$. For $\Theta > \Theta_R$, on the other hand, a single value of the impact parameter b corresponds to a single Θ_0 . Figure (II-9) also shows three trajectories with the same scattering angle.

FIGURA II-7

Fig. II-7 — Typical intermolecular potential (for Ar-H⁺): repulsive part, well and tail.

- FUNZIONE DI DEFLESSIONE $\Theta(b)$ COME FUNZIONE DEL PARAMETRO D'URTO b E CORRISPONDENTI TRAIETTORIE CLASSICHE.

FIGURA II-8

Fig. II-8 — Deflection function $\Theta(b)$ as a function of the impact parameter b and corresponding classical trajectories.

RAPPRESENTAZIONE DI 3 TRAIETTORIE CON LO STESSO ANGOLO DI DIFFUSIONE Θ_0 . IL CERCHIO RAPPRESENTA LA ZONA DOVE $W(R) > E$.

FIGURA II-9

Fig. II-9 — Representation of 3 trajectories with the same scattering angle Θ_0 . The circle represents the region where $W(R) > E$.

The angle Θ_R is called the Rainbow angle, in analogy with the optical scattering phenomenon giving rise to the rainbow, in which the exit angle of a light beam from a water droplet, as a function of the angle of incidence, exhibits a maximum analogous to that in Figure (II-9), which is responsible for the rainbow effect.

Near the Rainbow angle the classical differential cross section, given by the expression:

$$d\sigma(\Theta)/d\Omega = [1/\sin \Theta] \sum_i b_i |db_i/d\Theta| \quad (\text{II 2.58})$$

where the sum extends over the three values of the impact parameter that contribute to scattering at the same angle Θ , exhibits a singularity since for $\Theta = \Theta_R$, $\Theta(b)$ has a maximum (and hence $db/d\Theta$ diverges); in the quantum cross section the singularity that appears in the classical theory disappears, replaced by a maximum.

The multivaluedness of the deflection function for $\Theta < \Theta_R$ gives rise to interference phenomena caused by the superposition of waves that can be associated with the three impact parameters b_1 , b_2 and b_3 on the basis of semiclassical arguments. For $\Theta > \Theta_R$, on the other hand, such interference disappears and the classical and quantum cross sections present a similar appearance.

Being three in number, the interfering waves give rise to interference phenomena characterised, in principle, by three different frequencies.

This phenomenon can be shown starting directly from the quantum formula for the cross section in partial wave analysis:

$$f(\Theta) = (1/2ik) \sum_J (2J+1) P_J(\cos \Theta) [\exp(2i\delta_J) - 1] \quad (\text{II 2.59})$$

Since the semiclassical limit (for large values of J) of the Legendre polynomial $P_J(\cos \Theta)$ is (Landau Ch. XVII):

$$P_J(\cos \Theta) \rightarrow -i/\sqrt{[2\pi J \sin \Theta]} \left\{ \exp[i(J+1/2)\Theta + i\pi/4] \exp[-i(J+1/2)\Theta - i\pi/4] \right\} \quad (\text{II 2.60})$$

expression (II 2.59) tends to:

$$f(\Theta) = \sum_J \sqrt{[J/2\pi k \sin(\Theta)]} \left\{ \exp[i2\delta_J - i(J+1/2)\Theta - i\pi/4] - \exp[i2\delta_J + i(J+1/2)\Theta + i\pi/4] \right\} \quad (\text{II 2.61})$$

which, since the exponentials vary ever more rapidly as J increases, receives contributions mainly from those terms of the sum for which J renders the exponents stationary, namely those J such that:

$$2(d\delta_J/dJ) \pm \Theta = 0 \quad (\text{II 2.62})$$

In the semiclassical (JWKB) approximation the phase shift δ_J is determined as the difference between the phase of the semiclassical wave function:

$$\delta_{1J} = \int_r^\infty dR K_J(R) + \pi/4 \quad (\text{II 2.63})$$

where $K_J(R) = \sqrt{[2M(E - W_J(R))]/\hbar}$, and the phase shift of the free-particle wave:

$$\delta_{2J} = kR - J\pi/2 \quad (\text{II 2.64})$$

and is therefore given by:

$$\delta_J = \delta_{1J} - \delta_{2J} = \int_r^\infty dR [\sqrt{[2M(E - W_J(R))]/\hbar} - k] + \pi(J + 1/2)/2 - kr \quad (\text{II 2.65})$$

Performing the differentiation in (II 2.62) one obtains equation (II 2.56) which describes the classical trajectory, if the classical angular momentum bP is identified with $(J + 1/2)\hbar$.

For $\Theta < \Theta_R$ there are three values of J that render the exponents stationary, corresponding to the three rainbow trajectories, and equation (II 2.61) then reduces to the superposition of the three corresponding waves.

We note that equation (II 2.62) represents a semiclassical relation between the phase shift δ_J and the deflection function Θ : when the impact parameter $b \cong J/k$ is such that $\Theta > 0$, δ as a function of J appears to increase; for small values of b (of J) δ therefore increases with increasing J ; when, as b increases, Θ passes through its first zero, δ reaches a maximum and then decreases for all b for which $\Theta < 0$. At the Rainbow angle ($d\Theta/db = 0$) δ presents an inflection point.

The presence of interference structures in the differential cross section for $\Theta \cong \Theta_R$ therefore constitutes a powerful means of connecting the behaviour of the experimental cross sections with specific characteristics of the interaction potential. In Chapter III this will be illustrated with several examples.

APPENDIX II : THE NUMEROV METHOD

This is a brief technical chapter outlining the method of numerical propagation of the solution of the Schrödinger equation employed by the various computational programs used here (Smith Ch. 14, Gianturco Ch. V).

* * *

A differential equation relates the value Y that a function takes at a point X to the values it takes at infinitesimally neighbouring points.

For its numerical solution the differential equation must be transformed into a finite-difference equation on a finite set of points X_1, \dots, X_N , establishing a relation between the values Y_1, \dots, Y_N that the function takes on this set of points.

To fix ideas, let us take the second-order differential equation:

$$Y''(X) = f[X, Y(X)] \quad (\text{II A.1})$$

in whose class falls the radial or one-dimensional Schrödinger equation.

The differential equation (II A.1) can be transformed into a finite-difference equation by assuming that to first approximation the following equalities hold:

$$Y'(X_n) = (Y_n - Y_{n-1})/h \quad (\text{II A.2a})$$

$$Y''(X_n) = (Y_n - 2Y_{n-1} + Y_{n-2})/h^2 \quad (\text{II A.2b})$$

where h denotes, in this appendix, the integration step; one thus obtains a possible finite-difference equation for the differential equation (II A.1):

$$Y_n - 2Y_{n-1} + Y_{n-2} = h^2 f(X_n, Y_n) \quad (\text{II A.3})$$

To obtain a more accurate solution it is advisable, however, to correct equations (II A.2) by taking account in some way of all the neglected terms; strictly speaking, one would have:

$$(Y_n - Y_{n-1})/h = Y'(X_n) - Y''(X_n)h/2! + Y'''(X_n)h^2/3! - \dots \quad (\text{II A.4})$$

The Numerov method corrects equations (II A.2) with terms that depend only on the values of the second derivative Y'' , which is particularly suited to the class of equations (II A.1), as will be shown shortly.

We now derive the Numerov relations, starting from Newton's interpolation formula applied to the second derivative:

$$\begin{aligned} Y''(X) = & Y''_n + (\Delta_1 Y''_n/h)(X - X_n) + (\Delta_2 Y''_n/2!h^2)(X - X_n)(X - X_{n-1}) \\ & + (\Delta_3 Y''_n/3!h^3)(X - X_n)(X - X_{n-1})(X - X_{n-2}) + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (\text{II A.5})$$

where $\Delta_1 Y''_n = Y''_n - Y''_{n-1}$, $\Delta_2 Y''_n = Y''_n - 2Y''_{n-1} + Y''_{n-2}$, etc. are the finite differences of the second derivative.

It can easily be verified that this formula gives the correct value of Y'' at the

points X_n, X_{n-1}, \dots ; it provides an interpolation between these points and an extrapolation for $X > X_n$. During numerical integration X takes one of the values X_1, \dots, X_N , so one can set, without loss of generality:

$$X = X_N - Kh \quad (\text{II A.6})$$

where K is an integer; equation (II A.5) then becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} Y''(X_n - Kh) = Y''_{n-K} = Y''_n + \Delta_1 Y''(n)K \\ + \Delta_2 Y''_n K(K+1)/2! + \Delta_3 Y''_n K(K+1)(K+2)/3! + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (\text{II A.7})$$

Integrating this equation in dK twice and recalling that $dX = hdK$, hence $\int Y'' dK = Y'/h + \text{const.}$ and $\int Y' dK = Y/h + \text{const.}$, and choosing the two constants of integration so that $Y'(K=0) = Y'_n$ and $Y(K=0) = Y_n$, one obtains the following expression for Y_{n-K} :

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{n-K} = Y_n + hKY'_n + h^2 [K^2 Y''_n/2 + K^3 \Delta_1 Y''_n \\ + (K^3/12 + K^4/24) \Delta_2 Y''_n + (K^3/3 + K^4/4 + K^5/20) \Delta_3 Y''_n/6 \\ + (K^3 + 11K^4/12 + 3K^5/10 + K^6/30) \Delta_4 Y''_n] + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (\text{II A.9})$$

At this point one has an expression for Y_{n-K} in terms of the finite differences of the second derivative Y''_n alone. Setting $K=1$ and $K=2$ one can calculate Y_{n-1} and Y_{n-2} , from which the finite difference $\Delta_2 Y_n$ can be directly computed; up to powers of h^2 this is:

$$\Delta_2 Y_n/h^2 = Y''_{n-1} + \Delta_2 Y''_n/12 - \Delta_4 Y''_n/240 + O(h^4) \quad (\text{II A.9})$$

Substituting the values given by the differential equation (II A.1) for the second derivatives Y''_n , one finally obtains the Numerov relation for the values Y_n :

$$\Delta_2 Y_n/h^2 = f_{n-1} + \Delta_2 f_n/12 - \Delta_4 f_n/240 + \dots \quad (\text{II A.10})$$

where $f_n = f(X_n, Y_n)$.

In the case of the Schrödinger equation that we wish to solve, this equation expresses a linear relation between the value Y_n that the function takes at the point X_n and a number of values taken at adjacent points, the more the more terms are

retained in equation (II A.10). In that case one has:

$$f(X_n, Y_n) = c[W(X_n) - E]Y_n \quad \text{with} \quad C = \frac{2m}{\hbar^2} \quad (\text{II A.11})$$

where, if $\Psi(R)$ is the radial part of the wave function, $Y(R) = R\Psi(R)$. If the last term on the right-hand side of equation (II A.10) is neglected, only Y_n , Y_{n-1} and Y_{n-2} are involved, analogously to equation (3) but in a more accurate finite-difference equation.

Substituting (II A.11) into (II A.10) and expanding the finite difference $\Delta_2 Y_n''$ one finally obtains:

$$Y_n - 2Y_{n-1} + Y_{n-2} = ch^2[(E - W_n)Y_n + (5/6)(E - W_{n-1})Y_{n-1} + (E - W_{n-2})Y_{n-2}] \quad (\text{II A.12})$$

which can easily be inverted to give Y_n in terms of the two preceding points, or Y_{n-2} in terms of the two following points.

Chapter III

The Atom-Ion Interaction from Experimental Data

CHAPTER III-1 : GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS

The aim of this Chapter is to select the potentials that will be used in Chapter IV in the treatment of predissociation.

The choice of potential is an essential step in the study of molecules, yet a difficult one: even if its behaviour at small and large distances is known (Hirschfelder Ch. 13), its form in the region of greatest importance, that at intermediate distances, can be determined exactly only by solving the fixed-nucleus equation (I.2). At small distances the potential reduces to the electrostatic repulsion between the two nuclei, equal to $Z_1 Z_2 / R$ (in a.u.); for the $(R-H)^+$ systems this occurs at distances smaller than a few tenths of an atomic unit, where $Z_1 Z_2 / R \gg \varepsilon$, the depth of the potential well; at somewhat larger distances it is reasonable to expect that the nuclear charge of the noble gas atom is screened by the electron cloud and that the potential has the form:

$$V = Z_1' Z_2' e^{-R/a} / R \quad (\text{III 1.1})$$

At large distances, on the other hand, the residual interaction is represented by the polarisation interaction: the proton polarises the electron cloud of the noble gas atom and interacts with the multipole moments induced in the atom; of the various interactions, the one that decreases most slowly is the charge-induced dipole interaction, equal to $V_{\text{pol}} = -(1/2)\alpha E_p^2$, where α is the atomic polarisability of the atom and $E_p = e/R^2$ is the electrostatic field associated with the proton; the residual

interaction (in general for an ion-atom system) is therefore:

$$V_{\text{pol}} = -e^2\alpha/2R^4 \quad (\text{III 1.2})$$

This form has been taken as the “tail” of the potential $W(R)$ and has been connected to the inner part of the potential by a joining function centred at the point where the two parts of the potential meet.

What happens between the two asymptotic forms (III 1.1) and (III 1.2) depends directly on the strong interaction of the proton with the atom.

The determination of the potential in the intermediate region can be accomplished by solving equation (I.2), and a large part of quantum chemistry studies of molecular interactions are based on methods for solving the mathematical problem posed by equation (I.2); these calculations are however lengthy and complex and often yield the value of the potential only at a few values of the internuclear distance with an error associated with the approximation used to solve the fixed-nucleus equation.

As an alternative, direct inversion methods may be used; for example, the ingenious semiclassical KRR method of Klein, Rydberg and Rees (Mallard Ch. 7.3) allows $W(R)$ to be evaluated directly from the values E_n of the bound states with $J = 0$, describable by a function of the form:

$$E_n \cong E(N) = -\varepsilon + \omega_e N - x_e \omega_e N^2 \quad \text{with } N = n + 1/2 \quad (\text{III I.3})$$

Without going into its construction in detail, we note that it makes use of the following relations, valid in the semiclassical approximation:

$$R_B^{(n)} - R_A^{(n)} = (1/\sqrt{2\pi^2 M}) \int_0^N dN' 1/\sqrt{(E_n - E(N'))} \quad (\text{III I.4a})$$

$$1/R_A^{(n)} - 1/R_B^{(n)} = (1/\sqrt{2\pi^2 M}) \int_0^N dN' (B(N')M/\hbar^2)/\sqrt{(E_n - E(N'))} \quad (\text{III I.4b})$$

where $B(N) = B_e - \alpha_e N$ (B_e and α_e are two molecular constants discussed in greater detail in Chapter III-2) and where $R_A^{(n)}$ and $R_B^{(n)}$ are the two turning points associated with the energy of the eigenvalue E_n . From these two relations one can readily derive the values of the turning points $R_A^{(n)}$ and $R_B^{(n)}$ and hence the value of the potential at all turning points associated with the known eigenvalues ($W(R_A^{(n)}) = W(R_B^{(n)}) = E_n$).

Semiclassical direct inversion methods are also applicable to scattering data; for example, the Firsov method (Miller '69) extracts the phase shifts $\delta_J(E)$ from a

measurement of the differential cross section at a given energy E and uses them to obtain the interaction potential (for an application of this method to argon-proton scattering see Klingbeil '72). One must note, however, that a method of this type would be straightforwardly applicable only to a cross section measured with a resolution that is in practice never achievable; before applying it, a further processing of the data is therefore necessary to “clean” them of inaccuracies due to the finite resolution (in energy and angle) of the instruments.

Furthermore, the semiclassical approximations on which direct inversion methods are based can lead to results quite different from those obtainable by solving the fixed-nucleus equation. Moreover, none of the computational strategies described yields the potential directly in a simple analytical form, which would instead prove useful in numerical calculations and in comparative studies of similar systems.

One can therefore follow a strategy that lies in some sense halfway between the first two: one adopts a theoretical potential model depending on certain free parameters that are determined through a comparative study with the experimental data. This procedure translates into a continuous interaction between theory, which chooses the analytical form of the potential, and experiment, which fixes its parameters.

The experimental data that can be used may be of very different types, and in principle it is reasonable to expect that different sets of data will yield different potential parameters. This summarises what is essentially the main problem in inverting experimental data with a given analytical form of potential, namely the non-uniqueness of the extracted potential. Naturally the potentials extracted using different sets of data should be mutually consistent to within the order of the Born-Oppenheimer approximation; the various discrepancies that are found are attributable precisely to the assumption of a specific form for the potential model, which, although usually realistic, does not approach that of the true potential.

It should indeed be emphasised that a generic function $W(R)$ has infinitely many degrees of freedom, whereas the assumption of a specific form $W[\alpha, \beta, \dots; R]$ depending on some free parameters α, β, \dots selects from the set of possible potentials $\{W(R)\}$ a restricted class, however reasonably large the number of parameters may be.

As a significant example, the Lennard-Jones potential $\text{LJ}[2n, n] = \varepsilon(X^2 - 2X)$, with $X = R_e/R$, selects those potentials which, among other characteristics, decrease at large distances with a power of $1/R$ ($= n$) that is half of that with which they increase at small distances ($= 2n$).

Even more explicitly, one can say that for a potential depending, to fix ideas, on

three parameters, as in the case of the Morse potential $W(R) = \varepsilon(X^2 - 2X)$ with $X = \exp[b(1 - R/R_e)]$ which depends on ε , b and R_e , of the various derivatives calculated at $R = R_e$ and closely related to the molecular constants (see Chapter III 2), only the first three can be chosen arbitrarily by varying the parameters; but since all higher-order derivatives must depend uniquely on the same three parameters ε , b and R_e , adopting the Morse potential as a model for the potential means imposing an infinite series of conditions on the derivatives at R_e of order higher than three (and hence on the various molecular constants).

It thus follows that each set of experimental data leads to parameters that correctly describe the potential in those characteristics to which the set of data used is most sensitive. Spectroscopic data, for example, depend, especially when the quantum numbers of the states involved are not too high, only on the small oscillations of the nuclei around their equilibrium position R_e . Scattering data, by contrast, are sensitive to the overall form of the potential, but not to variations in sufficiently narrow regions, or to the tail of the potential if the energy is at least 1 eV. Other types of measurement, such as those of the diffusion coefficient or ionic mobility in gases (of H^+ in Ar or Ne, for example), performed at thermal energies, are extremely sensitive to the tail of the potential.

In confirmation of the non-uniqueness of the extracted potential, consider the equilibrium distance R_e : it is directly determined from spectroscopic data via the molecular constant B_e , and the rapid oscillations in the differential cross sections are also extremely sensitive to R_e because it closely controls the overall form of the potential; indeed both types of measurement have yielded values of R_e that are mutually consistent and consistent with ab initio calculations.

In what follows, attention will be restricted to experimental data from scattering experiments and data on bound states. In Section 2 of this chapter we shall illustrate how it is possible to determine the potential parameters from transitions and energies of the bound states. In Section 3 the experimental data used will be briefly listed, while in Section 4 comparisons and selections of the potentials will be made. General considerations will also be made on a broad class of potentials currently employed in the study of the interaction of neutral atoms, and their inadequacy for describing strongly interacting systems such as molecular ions will be demonstrated by an example; it will emerge that a simple alternative is represented by the “modified potentials”, which are also illustrated in Section 4.

CHAPTER III 2 :

USE OF DATA ON BOUND STATES

§1 : Bound-bound transitions

In order to introduce the method and to make some general remarks on transitions in diatomic molecules, we examine the lowest bound states, that is we consider the motion of the nuclei only in their small oscillations around the equilibrium distance R_e (Herzberg Ch. III).

In the small-oscillation approximation we can estimate the effective potential as follows:

$$W_J(R) \equiv W(R) + J(J+1)\hbar^2/2MR^2 \cong W_e + M\omega^2(R - R_e)^2/2 + B_e J(J+1) \quad (\text{III 2.1})$$

where $W_e = W(R_e)$, $M\omega^2 = W''(R_e)$ and $B_e = \hbar^2/2MR_e^2$ is the rotational constant. The eigenvalues of a Hamiltonian whose potential is written according to expression (III 2.1) turn out to be the sum of three distinct terms:

$$E(n, J) = W_e + \hbar\omega(n + 1/2) + B_e J(J + 1) \quad (\text{III 2.2})$$

The first term represents the energy of the motion of the electrons around the nuclei, since it is the minimum value of the potential curve corresponding to the electronic state in which the molecule finds itself. Energy differences between potential curves of different electronic states correspond to photons in the visible or ultraviolet part of the electromagnetic spectrum, and there one finds the “electronic transitions” (as already noted, we shall not consider such transitions but will restrict attention to the single electronic state $^1\Sigma^+$, and W_e will represent the depth of the potential well relative to the asymptotic value $W^\infty = W(R \rightarrow \infty)$).

The second term represents the energy of the small oscillations of the nuclei; in transitions between different vibrational states, the harmonic oscillator selection rule $\Delta n = \pm 1$ is in practice satisfied, even though the energies of the vibrational states correspond to regions of the intermolecular potential where it can no longer be considered harmonic. Vibrational transitions are then of order $\hbar\omega$, which being usually of the order of a thousand cm^{-1} places vibrational transitions in the infrared region.

The last term represents the rotational energy; every vibrational or rovibrational transition always involves a change in angular momentum due to the selection rule $\Delta J = \pm 1$, derivable from an analysis of the transition probability amplitude. This

is proportional to the matrix element of the molecular dipole moment between the initial and final states, and the angular part of this element (which contains the integration over the angles Θ and φ) is non-zero only if the two rovibrational states have an angular momentum J that differs by one unit. Rotational transitions are thus of order $B_e J$ and, since B_e is of the order of a few cm^{-1} , they occur in the microwave region.

Denoting by n_1 and n_2 the two vibrational quantum numbers involved in a transition and assuming $n_1 < n_2$, the following terminology is in use:

- $(n_1, J_1) \rightarrow (n_2, J_1 + 1)$ is said to belong to the R band and is denoted by the symbol $R(J_1)$;
- $(n_1, J_1) \rightarrow (n_2, J_1 - 1)$ is said to belong to the P band and is denoted by the symbol $P(J_1)$.

As thus defined, the R band can include transitions from $R(0)$ onwards, while the P band from $P(1)$ onwards, as schematically illustrated in Figure (III-1).

ILLUSTRAZIONE DELLA BANDA P E DELLA BANDA R.

FIGURA III-1

Fig. III-1 — Illustration of the P band and the R band.

For greater clarity we shall denote the transitions just mentioned by $R(n_1, J_1)$ and $P(n_1, J_1)$ respectively, understanding that $n_2 = n_1 + 1$, so as to keep track of the vibrational quantum number of the transition as well. In accordance with the simple expression (III 2.2), vibrational and rotational motions are independent, and

the transition energies of the R and P bands are given by:

$$R(n, J) = E(n + 1, J + 1) - E(n, J) = \hbar\omega + 2B_e(J + 1) \quad (\text{III 2.3a})$$

$$P(n, J) = E(n + 1, J - 1) - E(n, J) = \hbar\omega - 2B_eJ \quad (\text{III 2.3b})$$

In this approximation all R and P bands corresponding to different values of n are identical; however, formula (III 2.2), though correct in order of magnitude and providing a useful schematisation of the transitions, is not sufficiently accurate. It is well known that greater accuracy can be achieved by improving formula (III 2.2) with additional terms depending on n and J , as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} E(n, J) = & W_e + \omega_e(n + 1/2) + B_e[J(J + 1)] \\ & - \alpha_e(n + 1/2)[J(J + 1)] - x_e\omega_e(n + 1/2)^2 - D_e[J(J + 1)]^2 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{III 2.4})$$

where for convenience we have denoted the energy $\hbar\omega$ by ω_e .

The new molecular constants α_e , x_e , D_e , all having the dimensions of an energy, are smaller than the molecular constants ω_e and B_e by one or more orders of magnitude.

Increasing the number of molecular constants improves the precision with which the transitions can be described; in the case of equation (III 2.4), powers p_n of $(n + 1/2)$ and powers p_J of $[J(J + 1)]$ such that $p_n + p_J = 2$ have been included; the criterion for how many molecular constants are needed depends on the required accuracy. If, for example, one wishes to use expression (III 2.4), then the ratio $x_e\omega_e/\omega = x_e$ is an estimate of the percentage error incurred, which in this example is of the order of 1%. The following consideration regarding the expansion in powers of $(n + 1/2)$ and $[J(J + 1)]$ rather than in powers of $(n + 1/2)$ and J is also worth making: even though, for example, $B_e \ll \omega_e$, the constant B_e appears multiplied by $J(J + 1) \sim J^2$ while ω_e appears multiplied by $(n + 1/2) \sim n$, and the same applies to the other terms; for a typical potential it turns out that the values of the molecular constants are just such that if n_M and J_M represent the maximum quantum numbers of the bound states supported by the potential, then the following equations hold in order of magnitude:

$$\omega_e n_M \sim B_e J_M^2 \quad (\text{III 2.5a})$$

$$x_e \omega_e n_M^2 \sim \alpha_e n_M J_M \sim D_e J_M^2 \quad (\text{III 2.5b})$$

If the desired accuracy has not been achieved, further terms with $p_n + p_J = 3$ can be added, for which an analogous approximate equation holds. For our accuracy

requirements we shall see that the terms in expression (III 2.4) are sufficient to describe the bound states under discussion.

The molecular constants ω_e , B_e , α_e , $x_e\omega_e$, D_e , as defined, are all positive; thus as the vibrational quantum number n increases, $x_e\omega_e$ causes the levels (which for the harmonic oscillator would be equally spaced) to crowd together; it is worth recalling that the energies of the bound states with $J = 0$ of the Morse potential (Morse '29), $V(R) = \varepsilon[X^2(R) - 2X(R)]$ (with $X(R) = \exp[b(R_e - R)]$), which can be considered a realistic model intermolecular potential, are given exactly by the formula:

$$E(n, 0) = -\varepsilon + \omega_e(n + 1/2) - x_e\omega_e(n + 1/2)^2 \quad (\text{III 2.6})$$

which contains only the molecular constants ω_e and $x_e\omega_e$. The term $-\varepsilon$ represents the minimum of the potential W_e and the other two constants are given by $\omega_e = b\sqrt{[2\varepsilon/M]}$ and $x_e = \omega_e/4\varepsilon$ (see Figure (III-2)).

FIGURA III-2

Fig. III-2 — Morse potential and corresponding bound states with $J = 0$ ($\epsilon = 2.28 \text{ eV}$, $b = 1.00$, $R_e = 1 \text{ Å}$).

The molecular constant α_e couples vibrational and rotational motion; that they are not independent is evident from the fact that as J increases, the effective potential $W_J(R)$ is globally shifted upward, where the level-crowding effect is stronger and the form of the potential around the minimum is no longer the same, and hence the small oscillations are no longer the same either; the constant D_e finally corrects the centrifugal term $B_e[J(J+1)]$ of expression (III 2.2), since it represents an overestimate of the centrifugal energy; as J increases, the minimum of the effective potential $W_J(R)$ shifts to the right, the equilibrium distance between the two nuclei increases and hence the mean value of the centrifugal energy $\langle J(J+1)\hbar^2/2MR^2 \rangle$ decreases (see Figure (III-3) for the effect on W_J of increasing J).

FIGURA III-3

Fig. III-3 — Effective potentials for different angular momenta $J = 0, 15, 30, 45, 60, 75$.

From formulae (III 2.4) one can calculate the transition energies of the R and P bands:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R(n, J) &= E(n+1, J+1) - E(n, J) \\
 &= \omega_e - 2x_e\omega_e(n+1) + 2B_e(J+1) - 4D_e(J+1)^3 - \alpha_e(J+1)(2n+J+3)
 \end{aligned} \tag{III 2.7}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(n, J) &= E(n+1, J-1) - E(n, J) \\
 &= \omega_e - 2x_e\omega_e(n+1) - 2B_eJ + 4D_eJ^3 + \alpha_eJ(2n-J+2)
 \end{aligned} \tag{III 2.8}$$

These expressions suggest a simple method for determining the molecular constants from the spectroscopic data $R(n, J)$ and $P(n, J)$. Adding $P(n, J+1)$ and $R(n, J)$ one obtains:

$$S_n(J) = P(n, J+1) + R(n, J) = 2\omega_e - 4(n+1)x_e\omega_e - 2\alpha_e(J+1)^2 \tag{III 2.9}$$

It can be seen that through a linear fit or graphical methods, as a function of the independent variables n or J , one can extract α_e or $x_e\omega_e$ as slope coefficients and ω_e as the intercept at zero abscissa. One also obtains:

$$R(n, J) - P(n, J + 1) = 4B_e(J + 1) - 4\alpha_e(n + 1)(J + 1) - 8D_e(J + 1)^J \quad (\text{III 2.10a})$$

from which one derives:

$$D_n(J) = [R(n, J) - P(n, J)] / (J + 1) = 4B_e - 4\alpha_e(n + 1) - 8D_e(J + 1)^2 \quad (\text{III 2.10b})$$

which is analogous to (III 2.9) but allows one to extract α_e , B_e and D_e .

§2 : Determination of the potential well depth

When, as in the case of the (Ar-H)⁺ and (Ne-H)⁺ systems, the absolute values of the energies of some bound states are known, the molecular constants can be used to obtain information on the potential well depth ε . The experimental values E_n are known with certain experimental uncertainties ΔE_n , due at least to the finite energy resolution of the detectors; taking into account the fact that the energy differences are known with good precision through the spectroscopic transitions, it is possible to transform the errors ΔE_n into a single overall shift error on the various levels by performing a linear fit with the following expression:

$$E_n = -\varepsilon + \omega_e(n + 1/2) - x_e\omega_e(n + 1/2)^2 \quad (\text{III 2.11})$$

in which, since ε is the only unknown parameter, having determined the molecular constants ω_e and $x_e\omega_e$ with good precision from the spectroscopic data, it can be optimised so as to reproduce the energies of the known bound states.

* * *

§3 : Inversion of molecular constants

The molecular constants thus calculated from spectroscopic data evidently depend on the form of the intermolecular potential and can therefore provide information about it (Landau Ch. V).

If formulae (III 2.3) are used to describe the transitions, only the two molecular constants ω_e and B_e are extracted, yielding information on the second derivative of $W(R)$ at $R = R_e$, namely $W_e'' (= M\omega^2)$, and on the equilibrium distance $R_e (= \hbar/\sqrt{2MB_e})$.

With more molecular constants available, more and more precise information on the intermolecular potential can be extracted.

To this end we perform an expansion of the effective potential $W_J(R)$ around $R = R_e$, including a few more terms than in the expansion of expression (III 2.1), in the variable $\xi = R - R_e$:

$$\begin{aligned} W_J(R) &= W(R) + J(J+1)\hbar^2/2MR^2 \\ &\cong W_e + M\omega^2\xi^2/2 + a\xi^3 + b\xi^4 \\ &\quad + B_e[J(J+1)] - 2B_e[J(J+1)]\xi/R_e + 3B_e[J(J+1)]\xi^2/R_e^2 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{III 2.12})$$

$W(R)$ has been expanded up to the fourth power of ξ (a and b are the expansion coefficients) and the centrifugal term up to the second power of ξ . If we now regard:

$$H_0 = W_e + M\omega^2\xi^2/2 + B_e[J(J+1)] \quad (\text{III 2.13})$$

as the unperturbed Hamiltonian, for which we already have an exact expression for the eigenvalues (given by equation (III 2.2)), and set:

$$H_1 = a\xi^3 + b\xi^4 - 2B_e[J(J+1)]\xi/R_e + 3B_e[J(J+1)]\xi^2/R_e^2 \quad (\text{III 2.14})$$

treating it as a small perturbation to H_0 , we can use time-independent perturbation theory to calculate the corrections to expression (III 2.2) generated by H_1 . The final expression will be similar to expression (III 2.4) and will contain powers of $(n+1/2)$ and $[J(J+1)]$ arising from the corrections at the various orders.

For consistency with the assumption made in expression (III 2.4), the perturbative calculation should be stopped where terms with $p_n + p_J > 2$ begin to appear. We note at once, therefore, that this would have already occurred at first order in expressions (III 2.12) or (III 2.14) had we considered powers of ξ greater than 4 in the expansion of $W(R)$ and powers simply greater than 2 for the centrifugal term (which already contains a $[J(J+1)]$). The same would occur in any case if the perturbative calculation were carried beyond second order.

We therefore estimate the perturbed eigenvalue E_n , from which in this chapter we shall omit the index J since in the calculation we are about to perform of the perturbation to a one-dimensional harmonic oscillator the quantum number J is

treated as a parameter, as given by:

$$E_n = E_n^{(0)} + E_n^{(1)} + E_n^{(2)} \quad \text{where:} \quad (\text{III 2.15a})$$

$$E_n^{(0)} = W_e + \omega_e(n + 1/2) + B_e[J(J + 1)] \quad (\text{III 2.15b})$$

$$E_n^{(1)} = \langle n | H_1 | n \rangle \quad (\text{III 2.15c})$$

$$E_n^{(2)} = \sum'_m |\langle n | H_1 | m \rangle|^2 / [E_m^0 - E_n^0] = \sum'_m |\langle n | H_1 | m \rangle|^2 / [(m - n)\omega_e] \quad (\text{III 2.15d})$$

The first-order correction is evaluated as:

$$\langle n | H_1 | m \rangle = \int dx \psi_n(x) H_1 \psi_m(x) \quad (\text{III 2.16})$$

where ψ_n are the normalised eigenfunctions of the harmonic oscillator:

$$\psi_n(x) = [1/\sqrt{(\pi^{1/2} x_0 2^n n!)}] H_n(y) \exp(-y^2/2) \quad \text{with } x_0 = \sqrt{(\hbar/M\omega)}, \quad y = x/x_0 \quad (\text{III 2.17})$$

and $H_n(y)$ are the Hermite polynomials:

$$H_n(y) = (-1)^n [\exp(y^2)] (d/dy)^n [\exp(-y^2)] \quad (\text{III 2.17d})$$

Using the recurrence formula for Hermite polynomials:

$$yH_n(y) = nH_{n-1}(y) + (1/2)H_{n+1}(y) \quad (\text{III 2.19})$$

one can easily show that the matrix elements $\langle n | \xi | n \rangle$ and $\langle n | \xi^3 | n \rangle$ vanish, and that using (III 2.16) and (III 2.17):

$$\langle n | \xi^2 | n \rangle = x_0^2(n + 1/2) \quad (\text{III 2.19})$$

$$\langle n | \xi^4 | n \rangle = x_0^4(n^2 + n + 1/2) \quad (\text{III 2.20})$$

The first-order correction is therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} E_n^{(1)} &= \langle n | H_1 | n \rangle = \langle n | a\xi^3 + b\xi^4 - 2B_e J(J + 1)\xi/R_e + 3B_e J(J + 1)\xi^2/R_e^2 | n \rangle \\ &= 3b(\hbar/m\omega)^2(n^2 + n + 1/2)/2 + 6(B_e^2/\hbar\omega)[J(J + 1)](n + 1/2) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{III 2.21})$$

The sum appearing in the second-order correction term, running over all $m \neq n$, will contain terms with $m = n \pm 1$, $m = n \pm 2$, $m = n \pm 3$ and $m = n \pm 4$, since these are the only ones for which the matrix element of H_1 does not vanish.

Of these various terms, however, only those with $m = n \pm 1$ and $m = n \pm 3$ need

be considered, since the others would give $p_n + p_J > 2$:

$$E_n^{(2)} = |\langle n|H_1|n-1\rangle|^2/\hbar\omega - |\langle n|H_1|n+1\rangle|^2/\hbar\omega \\ + |\langle n|H_1|n-3\rangle|^2/3\hbar\omega - |\langle n|H_1|n+3\rangle|^2/3\hbar\omega \quad (\text{III 2.22})$$

In the matrix elements of the last two terms only $a\xi^3$ contributes, while in the first two both the 1st and 3rd powers of ξ contribute; making use of the (symmetric) matrix elements:

$$\langle n|\xi|n-1\rangle = x_0\sqrt{[n/2]} \quad \text{and hence} \quad \langle n|\xi|n+1\rangle = x_0\sqrt{[(n+1)/2]} \quad (\text{III 2.23a})$$

$$\langle n|\xi^3|n-1\rangle = x_0^3\sqrt{[9n^3/8]}, \quad \langle n|\xi^3|n+1\rangle = x_0^3\sqrt{[9(n+1)^3/8]} \quad (\text{III 2.23b})$$

$$\langle n|\xi^3|n-3\rangle = x_0^3\sqrt{[n(n-1)(n-2)/8]}, \\ \langle n|\xi^3|n+3\rangle = x_0^3\sqrt{[(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)/8]} \quad (\text{III 2.23c})$$

one obtains for $E_n^{(2)}$ the following expression:

$$E_n^{(2)} = -(15x_0^6a^2/4\hbar\omega)(n^2 + n + 11/30) \\ - (2B_e x_0^2/\hbar\omega R_e^2)[J(J+1)]^2 + (6ax_0^4B_e/\hbar\omega R_e)(n+1/2)[J(J+1)] \quad (\text{III 2.24})$$

Finally, summing $E_n^{(0)}$, $E_n^{(1)}$ and $E_n^{(2)}$ we obtain the corrected eigenvalue $E(n, J)$:

$$E(n, J) = W_e + \hbar\omega(n+1/2) + B_e J(J+1) \\ - (3/2)(\hbar/m\omega)^2[5a^2/2M\omega^2 - b](n+1/2)^2 \\ - (2B_e/\hbar\omega)^2[J(J+1)]^2 \\ + (6B_e^2/\hbar\omega)[1 + 2aR_e/M\omega^2](n+1/2)[J(J+1)] \quad (\text{III 2.25})$$

where the term depending neither on n nor on J has been included in W_e .

We can finally compare the formula obtained with expression (III 2.4) and, by equating the coefficients of powers of $(n+1/2)$ and $[J(J+1)]$, obtain the relations:

$$\omega_e = \hbar\sqrt{[W_e''/M]} = R_e\sqrt{[2W_e''/B_e]} \quad (\text{III 2.26a})$$

$$B_e = \hbar^2/2MR_e^2 \quad (\text{III 2.26b})$$

$$x_e\omega_e = (3/2)(\hbar/M\omega)^2[5a^2/2M\omega^2 - b] \quad (\text{III 2.26c})$$

$$\alpha_e = -(6B_e^2/\hbar\omega)[1 + 2aR_e/m\omega^2] \quad (\text{III 2.26d})$$

$$D_e = (2B_e/\hbar\omega)^2 \quad (\text{III 2.26e})$$

It can be seen that through the molecular constants we are now able to read off information about the second derivative $W_e'' (= M\omega^2)$, the third ($= 3!a$), the fourth ($= 4!b$), and the equilibrium distance R_e . This information can be used to directly construct the intermolecular potential. The last equation can be used as a consistency check of the calculation and is usually well satisfied.

The procedure just described, for the case where one restricts to $p_n + p_J = 2$, can be regarded as a particular case of a general procedure called the ‘‘Dunham expansion’’; this consists of a generalisation of expression (III 2.4) in which the energy eigenvalues are expressed according to the following series (Dunham '32, Herzberg Ch. III, Townes Ch.):

$$E(n, J) = \sum_{i,k} Y_{ik} (n + 1/2)^i [J(J + 1)]^k \quad (\text{III 2.27})$$

where the Y_{ik} are constants (Dunham coefficients) that are directly related to R_e and to the derivatives $W_e^{(n)}$ of the potential by relations analogous to (III 2.26) but, if the sum is extended to values of i and k such that $i_{\text{MAX}} + k_{\text{MAX}} > 2$, are much more complex, even though they provide information on derivatives of order higher than four. To first approximation, comparison of expression (III 2.27) with expression (III 2.4) shows that $Y_{10} \cong \omega_e$, $Y_{01} \cong B_e$, $Y_{20} \cong x_e \omega_e$, ... etc.

Before inverting relations (III 2.26), it is convenient to introduce, in order to simplify the expressions, different coefficients from those used for expanding $W(R)$ in powers of ξ ($W \cong W_e + M\omega^2 \xi^2/2 + a\xi^3 + b\xi^4 + \dots$), which are defined through the following expansion:

$$W(R) = W_e + a_0 \xi_D^2 (1 + a_1 \xi_D + a_2 \xi_D^2 + \dots) \quad (\text{III 2.28})$$

where $\xi_D = (R - R_e)/R_e$ is the Dunham variable. Comparing the two different series expansions, one obtains the following relations:

$$a_0 = M\omega^2 R_e^2/2 = \omega_e^2/4B_e \quad (\text{III 2.29a})$$

$$a_1 = W_e''' R_e^3/3! a_0 = a R_e^3/a_0 \quad (\text{III 2.29b})$$

$$a_2 = W_e^{IV} R_e^4/4! a_0 = b R_e^4/a_0 \quad (\text{III 2.29c})$$

In terms of these constants, equations (III 2.26) are written as follows:

$$\omega_e = \sqrt{[2W_e''R_e^2B_e]} \quad (\text{III 2.30a})$$

$$B_e = 1/2MR_e^2 \quad \text{with } M, R_e \text{ in a.u.} \quad (\text{III 2.30b})$$

$$x_e\omega_e = (3B_e/2)(5a_1^2/4 - a_2) \quad (\text{III 2.30c})$$

$$\alpha_e = -(6B_e^2/\omega_e)(1 + a_1) \quad (\text{III 2.30d})$$

$$D_e = 4B_e^3/\omega_e^2 \quad (\text{III 2.30e})$$

which we can invert to obtain the following expressions:

$$R_e = 1/\sqrt{[2MB_e]} \quad (M, R_e \text{ in a.u.}) \quad (\text{III 2.31a})$$

$$2a_0 = \omega_e^2/2B_e \quad (\text{III 2.31b})$$

$$a_1 = -[1 + \alpha_e\omega_e/6B_e^2] \quad (\text{III 2.31c})$$

$$a_2 = 5a_1^2/4 - 2x_e\omega_e/3B_e \quad (\text{III 2.31d})$$

which together with the relations:

$$W_e''R_e^2 = 2a_0 \quad (\text{III 2.32a})$$

$$W_e'''R_e^3 = 3! a_0a_1 \quad (\text{III 2.32b})$$

$$W_e^{IV}R_e^4 = 4! a_0a_2 \quad (\text{III 2.32c})$$

allow one to extract W_e'' , W_e''' , W_e^{IV} and R_e from spectroscopic data.

* * *

CHAPTER III 3 : EXPERIMENTAL DATA

Information on protonated noble gases comes to us from experiments of various types, some of which present practical difficulties in their realisation such that they have only recently been carried out with sufficient accuracy.

The phenomenology concerning the helium-proton interaction is more extensive than that of the other protonated noble gases and includes, in addition, some experiments that will be taken up again later in connection with the calculations concerning resonant states.

In this chapter, however, only the results of experiments carried out to study the interaction between protons and atoms of neon, argon and krypton will be presented. These will provide the information and criteria needed to select the intermolecular

potentials to be used in the calculations on resonant states.

* * *

§1 : Spectroscopic transitions

The study of transitions between the various bound states presents great practical difficulties related to the impossibility of achieving sufficiently high densities of $(R-H)^+$ to easily detect their spectra.

Using different techniques, some of the R and P bands have been detected for $(Ne-H)^+$, $(Ar-H)^+$, $(Kr-H)^+$ and analogous systems obtained with isotopes of the constituent atoms, which are listed in the Appendix to Chapter III together with the other experimental data (Wong '82, Brault '82, Johns '84, Bowman '83).

The precision of these measurements is extremely high (up to 1 part in 10^9) and is therefore much greater than what would be sufficient in a study based on the Born-Oppenheimer approximation.

Using linear fits in the manner described in Chapter III 1, the molecular constants ω_e , $x_e\omega_e$, α_e , B_e and D_e have been determined, whose values are reported in Table III.1.

TABELLA III: 1			
COSTANTI MOLECOLARI	$({}_{20}\text{Ne-H})^+$	$({}_{40}\text{Ar-H})^+$	$({}_{84}\text{Kr-H})^+$
ω_e	2900 cm^{-1}	2710.92 cm^{-1}	2494.654 cm^{-1}
$\omega_e x_e$	111 cm^{-1}	61.64 cm^{-1}	48.53 cm^{-1}
B_e	17.88 cm^{-1}	10.4613 cm^{-1}	8.3814 cm^{-1}
R_e	0.9913 \AA	1.28 \AA	1.422 \AA
α_e	1.08 cm^{-1}	0.37877 cm^{-1}	0.26707 cm^{-1}
D_e	$2.704 \times 10^{-3} \text{cm}^{-1}$	$0.62303 \times 10^{-3} \text{cm}^{-1}$	$0.3779 \times 10^{-3} \text{cm}^{-1}$

 Table III:1 — Molecular constants for $({}_{20}\text{Ne-H})^+$, $({}_{40}\text{Ar-H})^+$, $({}_{84}\text{Kr-H})^+$.

In the case of $(\text{Ne-H})^+$, however, the fact that only some transitions of the fundamental bands $R(0, J)$ and $P(0, J)$ have been detected would not have allowed the determination of the molecular constants ω_e and $x_e\omega_e$ separately, but only the difference $(1 - 2x_e)\omega_e$, as can be derived from expressions (III 2.7) and (III 2.8). Since, however, these have been detected both for the $({}^{20}\text{Ne-H})^+$ system and for the $({}^{22}\text{Ne-H})^+$ system containing the neon isotope ${}^{22}\text{Ne}$, it has been possible to use the isotopic dependence of the molecular constants to determine ω_e and $x_e\omega_e$ separately.

It can be seen from equations (III 2.26) that while $\omega_e \propto 1/\sqrt{M}$, $x_e\omega_e$ does not depend on the reduced mass of the molecule ($M\omega^2 = W_e''$ depends only on the form of the potential) and should therefore be independent of the types of isotopes that make up the molecule. Expressing the dependence of the frequency on the reduced mass by writing $\omega_e = \omega^0/\sqrt{M}$ and denoting by $\Delta(20)$ and $\Delta(22)$ the two aforementioned differences determined from the transitions of $({}^{20}\text{Ne-H})^+$ and $({}^{22}\text{Ne-H})^+$ respectively

(whose masses we denote by M_{20} and M_{22}):

$$\Delta(20) = \omega^\circ / \sqrt{M_{20}} - 2x_e\omega_e \quad (\text{III 3.1a})$$

$$\Delta(22) = \omega^\circ / \sqrt{M_{22}} - 2x_e\omega_e \quad (\text{III 3.1b})$$

Taking the difference of the two equations one obtains:

$$\omega^\circ = [\Delta(20) - \Delta(22)] / [1/\sqrt{M_{20}} - 1/\sqrt{M_{22}}] \quad (\text{III 3.2})$$

From ω° one can then easily extract ω_e and $x_e\omega_e$.

In Figure (III-4) a graph is shown, by way of example, of the quantities $S_n(J)$ and $D_n(J)$ defined in Chapter III 2 (Eqs. (III 2.9) and (III 2.10b)) as a function of J , calculated from the spectroscopic lines of $(^{40}\text{Ar-H})^+$.

* * *

FIGURA III-4

Fig. III-4 — Graphical determination of molecular constants: representation of the quantities $S_n(J)$ and $D_n(J)$, as defined in Chapter III 2, as a function of $(J + 1)^2$ for $J = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$.

§2 : Energies of bound states

An experiment, so far carried out only for the $(\text{Ne-H})^+$ and $(\text{Ar-H})^+$ systems, has studied the associative ionisation of the hydrogen atom with a noble gas atom

(Lorenzen '80, Lorenzen '81):

Briefly, the study of reaction (III 3.3) was carried out using a scattering experiment in which a beam of R^* atoms produced in the excited state $np^5(n+1)s$ ($n = 2$ for $\text{R} = \text{neon}$, $n = 3$ for $\text{R} = \text{argon}$) is made to collide against a target consisting of a mixture of H and H_2 . After reaction (III 3.3) has occurred, the electron produced in the associative ionisation is detected and its energy spectrum is recorded with a high-resolution multichannel analyser ($\cong 20$ meV).

Referring all energies to that of the separated H and R atoms, energy conservation for reaction (III 3.3), seen from the centre-of-mass reference frame, is written as:

$$\Delta E^* + K_i = -|B_{n,J}| + |W| + K_e \quad (\text{III } 3.4)$$

where ΔE^* is the excitation energy of $\text{R} \rightarrow \text{R}^*$,

K_i the relative kinetic energy of R^* and H ,

$|B_{n,J}|$ the magnitude of the binding energy of the formed system $(\text{R-H})^+$,

W the ionisation potential of the reaction $\text{H} + W \rightarrow \text{H}^+ + e^-$ (at rest),

K_e the kinetic energy of the produced electron, and where the kinetic energy of $(\text{R-H})^+$ has been neglected since the small mass of the electron allows one to neglect, in the centre of mass, the kinetic energy $P_0^2/2M$ of $(\text{R-H})^+$ compared with $P_0^2/2m_e$ of the electron. One thus finds that the electron energy spectrum as a function of the initial energy K_i :

$$K_e(n, J) = \Delta E^* + K_i - |W| + |B(n, J)| \quad (\text{III } 3.5)$$

reveals a structure corresponding to the various bound states with vibrational and rotational quantum numbers n and J of the formed molecule.

The importance of this experiment lies in the fact that the spectra (reported in the Appendix to Chapter III) allow, once the other energies in expression (III 3.5) are known, the absolute value $B(n, J)$ of the binding energy of the $(\text{R-H})^+$ system (relative to the energy possessed by the two separated atoms R , H^+) to be obtained. In particular, we report in Table III:2 the first bound states with $J = 0$ and $n > 0$.

TABELLA III: 2				
$E(n,0)$	$(\text{Ne-H})^+$	$(\text{Ar-H})^+$	$(\text{Ne-D})^+$	$(\text{Ar-D})^+$
$n = 1$	$(1772 \pm 28) \text{meV}$	$(3538 \pm 30) \text{meV}$	—	—
2	1456 ± 22	3241 ± 22	—	$(3454 \pm 30) \text{meV}$
3	1186 ± 22	2947 ± 22	$(1455 \pm 30) \text{meV}$	3240 ± 24
4	934 ± 27	2665 ± 24	1256 ± 24	3026 ± 24
5	—	2402 ± 26	1068 ± 26	2825 ± 24
6	—	—	896 ± 30	2624 ± 26
7	—	—	734 ± 30	2429 ± 28
8	—	—	—	2236 ± 32
ε	$(2276 \pm 32) \text{meV}$	$(4018 \pm 30) \text{meV}$	$(2265 \pm 34) \text{meV}$	(4032 ± 43)

Table III:2 — Energies of bound states $E(n,0)$ for $(\text{Ne-H})^+$, $(\text{Ar-H})^+$, $(\text{Ne-D})^+$, $(\text{Ar-D})^+$ (in meV).

Using the values of ω_e and $x_e\omega_e$ for $(\text{Ar-H})^+$ and $(\text{Ne-H})^+$ measured in this experiment, it has been possible to carry out the optimisation to determine ε as described in §2 of Chapter III 2. We report in Table III:2 also the values of ε obtained by performing this optimisation.

§3 : Differential cross sections

A series of measurements of the elastic differential cross section for protons scattered from neon, argon and krypton has also been available since 1971.

The energy range explored does not exceed 30 eV, precisely in order to remain in the elastic scattering regime. All the various experiments have been performed with more or less the same apparatus geometry, namely with a source of energy-selected protons colliding with a target consisting of a noble gas sample; the count of scattered protons as a function of the scattering angle is then performed with a

detector capable of rotating around the target.

The angular resolution of the apparatus, however, was not sufficient in the case of some measurements to allow the detection of the rapid oscillations described in Chapter II-2, of which a kind of average was instead observed. The more recent measurements, on the other hand, have been able to resolve even the fastest oscillations, providing an excellent point of comparison with the theoretical calculations.

All experimental graphs of the differential cross sections are reported in the Appendix to Chapter III and are listed in Table III.3 together with the bibliographic source.

TABELLA III: 3			
BIBLIOGRAFIA	SISTEMA DI RIFERIMENTO	ENERGIA (eV)	RANGE (GRADI)
Ne-H⁺:			
MITTMAN '71	LAB.	6.6	0° ÷ 35°
GIANTURCO '86	LAB.	14.8	0° ÷ 20°
KONRAD '83	C.M.	5.14	0° ÷ 45°
KONRAD '83	C.M.	1.90	0° ÷ 130°
Ar-H⁺:			
MITTMAN '70	LAB.	10.7	0° ÷ 35°
MITTMAN '70	LAB.	20.0	0° ÷ 20°
MITTMAN '70	LAB.	29.8	0° ÷ 13°
RICH '71	C.M.	5.0	0° ÷ 70°
GIANTURCO '86	LAB.	14.8	0° ÷ 30°
KONRAD '83	C.M.	4.7	0° ÷ 70°
Kr-H⁺			
MITTMAN '71	LAB	15.8	0° ÷ 25°
MITTMAN '71	LAB	30.3	0° ÷ 15°
GIANTURCO '86	LAB	14.8	0° ÷ 30°

Table III:3 — List of scattering experiments for Ne-H⁺, Ar-H⁺, Kr-H⁺: references, reference frame, energy (eV) and range (degrees).

Chapter III 4: Selection of the Potential

The importance of choosing an appropriate potential model is self-evident; from a potential that is not realistic, no predictions that are even approximately in agreement with the data can be made, for any values of its parameters.

In the past, potentials of very simple form such as the Morse or Lennard-Jones

potential were used with a degree of success relative to the experimental information then available; the subsequent availability of new and more precise data (derived from e.m. spectra, from beam-scattering experiments, from measurements of the viscosity coefficient and the virial coefficient) revealed their inadequacy.

Moreover, regarding the particular case of the Lennard-Jones potential $LJ(m, n)$ given by:

$$LJ(m, n) = \varepsilon [n\rho^{-m} - m\rho^{-n}] / (m - n), \quad \rho = R/R_e \quad (\text{III 4.1})$$

it turns out that a power-law behaviour in $1/R$ is particularly well suited to describing weakly interacting systems, such as Ar-Ar (systems in which the interaction is mainly due to mutual polarisation), as has been verified in the past, but in any case not with the precision needed to account for all the measurement results (see Maitland Ch. 9). A power-law behaviour is not realistic, however, for describing systems that interact strongly via valence forces or such as atom-ion systems; for these systems, as confirmed among other things by the estimates from ab initio calculations, exponential-type behaviours, such as those of the Morse potential, are to be preferred. Analytical potential models are usually presented in reduced form:

$$W(R) = \varepsilon U(\rho) \quad (\text{III 4.2})$$

where ε is the well depth and $U(\rho)$ is a function that depends only on the reduced variable $\rho = R/R_e$ and that satisfies the condition:

$$U(1) = -1 = \text{MINIMUM} \quad (\text{III 4.3})$$

For the rest, the form of U is determined solely by a series of dimensionless parameters α, β, \dots

Suppose now we wish to use the theory of Chapter III.3 to construct the potential. To this end we must make use of equations (III 2.31) and (III 2.32) from which it is possible to extract R_e and the derivatives $\varepsilon U''$, $\varepsilon U'''$ and εU^{IV} evaluated at $R = R_e$; to be able to use this information it is necessary to have a potential with at least 4 parameters with which to solve the system:

$$U''(R = R_e) = W_e'' / \varepsilon \quad (\text{III 4.4a})$$

$$U'''(R = R_e) = W_e''' / \varepsilon \quad (\text{III 4.4b})$$

$$U^{IV}(R = R_e) = W_e^{IV} / \varepsilon \quad (\text{III 4.4c})$$

$$R_e = 1 / \sqrt{2MB_e} \quad (M, B_e \text{ in a.u.}) \quad (\text{III 4.4d})$$

The Morse potential therefore could not be used since it depends on only three parameters.

On the other hand, it is also incorrect to use a potential with exactly 4 parameters; as it is reasonable to expect and as has been explicitly verified by numerical tests on the potential:

$$W(R) = \varepsilon[X^2(\rho) - 2X(\rho)] \quad \text{with } \rho = R/R_e$$

$$X(\rho) = (1/\rho^a) \exp[b(1 - \rho)] \quad (\text{III 4.5})$$

which depends on exactly 4 parameters ε , R_e , a , b , it is not realistic to determine a parameter such as ε , which influences the entire form of the potential, from a few derivatives evaluated at $R = R_e$.

The potential well depth ε will instead be determined according to the procedure described in §2 of Chapter III 2, which uses the energies of the bound states and the molecular constants, that is, the values reported in Table III.2.

Taking into account furthermore that the determination of R_e proceeds through a single molecular constant ($R_e = 1/\sqrt{2mB_e}$) and is decoupled from the determinations of the derivatives of W at R_e , one can see the usefulness of writing the potential in the reduced form (III 4.2), which shows explicitly the dependence of the potential on R_e and ε .

Once R_e and ε have been determined, three of equations (III 4.4) remain to be used to determine the parameters of the potential; if we use the 5-parameter potential: $W(R) = \varepsilon[X^2(\rho) - 2X(\rho)]$ with $\rho = R/R_e$

$$X(\rho) = (1/\rho^a) \exp[b(1 - \rho) + c(1 - \rho^2)/2] \quad (\text{III 4.6})$$

the first three equations (III 4.4) become:

$$W_e'' = 2\varepsilon(a + b + c)^2 \quad (\text{III 4.7a})$$

$$W_e''' = -\varepsilon 6(a + b + c)^3 - 6(c - a)(a + b + c)\varepsilon \quad (\text{III 4.7b})$$

$$W_e^{IV} = \varepsilon 14(a + b + c)^4 + 36(a + b + c)^2(c - a)\varepsilon + 6(c - a)^2\varepsilon + 16a(a + b + c)\varepsilon \quad (\text{III 4.7c})$$

which can easily be inverted to extract a, b, c as functions of the known values W_e'' , W_e''' , W_e^{IV} . The values of the parameters obtained for $(\text{Ar-H})^+$ and for $(\text{Ne-H})^+$ are reported in the following table:

Table III.4 — Trial Potential 1

	(Ne-H) ⁺	(Ar-H) ⁺
ε	2.27 eV	4.03 eV
R_e	0.9914 Å	1.28 Å
a	1.279	1.00
b	0.1883	0.8846
c	1.0482	0.444

The potentials given by equation (III 4.6) with the parameters of Table III.4 showed excellent agreement with the energies of the bound states and the spectroscopic transitions, whose comparison is reported in columns I and VI of Tables III.5 (the

TABELLA III:5A ($^{20}\text{Ne-H}^+$) STATI LEGATI E TRANSIZIONI

	I : EXPER.		II : MITTMAN		III : KONRAD		IV : G. T.		V : ROSMUS		VI : PROVA 1		VII : PROVA 2	
	$(E \pm \Delta E)$	$\Delta E/E$	$E(\text{cm}^{-1})$	ΔE_{exp}	$E(\text{cm}^{-1})$	ΔE_{exp}	$E(\text{cm}^{-1})$	ΔE_{exp}						
\mathcal{E}	$2.275 \pm 0.025 \text{ eV}$		2.28 eV		2.30 eV		2.283 eV		2.27 eV		2.28 eV		2.28 eV	
R_e	0.992 \AA		0.99 \AA		0.996 \AA		0.996 \AA		0.9914 \AA		0.996 \AA		0.996 \AA	
$E(0,0)$	16946 ± 225	1.3%	17007	0.4%	16926	0.1%	16987	0.24%	16884	0.37%	16972	0.15%	16972	0.15%
$E(1,0)$	14292 ± 225	1.5%	14553	1.7%	14200	0.6%	13912	2.6%	14208	0.6%	14248	0.3%	14248	0.3%
$E(2,0)$	11816 ± 177	1.5%	12115	2.5%	11717	0.8%	11225	5.0%	11918	0.8%	11753	0.2%	11752	0.2%
$E(3,0)$	9566 ± 177	1.8%	9999	4.5%	9479	0.9%	8851	7.5%	9670	1.37%	9520	0.48%	9592	0.28%
$E(4,0)$	7533 ± 218	2.8%	8096	7.5%	7482	0.7%	6782	10%	7688	2.1%	7507	0.34%	7643	1.46%
$\lambda(0,6)$	$2856.341(2)$		2218.0 cm^{-1}	4.8%	2898.3 cm^{-1}	1.5%	3185.1 cm^{-1}	11.5%	2892.3 cm^{-1}	0.8%	2855.3	0.036%	2897.0	1.4%
$\lambda(0,5)$	$2838.453(5)$		2702.8	4.8%	2881.2	4.5%	3168.2	11.6%	2812.6	0.9%	2877.0	0.041%	2880.0	1.5%
$\lambda(0,4)$	$2817.427(3)$		2684.8	4.3%	2861.5	4.6%	3148.6	11.8%	2790.5	1.0%	2816.1	0.046%	2860.3	1.5%
$\lambda(0,3)$	$2794.224(0)$		2664.0	4.6%	2839.2	4.6%	3126.4	11.9%	2766.2	1.0%	2792.8	0.05%	2838.0	1.6%
$\lambda(0,2)$	$2768.603(4)$		2640.4	4.6%	2814.5	4.7%	3101.7	12%	2739.7	1.0%	2767.1	0.051%	2813.2	1.7%
$\lambda(0,1)$	$2740.626(2)$		2614.0	4.6%	2787.3	4.7%	3074.4	12.2%	2711.2	1.1%	2739.1	0.057%	2785.9	1.8%
$\lambda(0,0)$	2710.3557		2585.0	4.6%	2757.7	4.7%	3044.8	12.4%	2680.6	1.1%	2708.7	0.059%	2756.2	1.8%
$\lambda(0,1)$	$2643.191(0)$		2519.3	4.7%	2691.6	4.8%	2978.3	12.3%	2643.7	1.1%	2641.5	0.063%	2689.8	1.8%
$\lambda(0,2)$	$2606.423(9)$		2482.6	4.8%	2655.3	4.9%	2941.7	12.9%	2577.5	1.1%	2604.8	0.063%	2653.2	1.8%
$\lambda(0,3)$	$2567.620(9)$		2443.6	4.8%	2616.7	4.9%	2902.8	13%	2539.5	1.1%	2566.0	0.063%	2614.5	1.8%
$\lambda(0,4)$	$2526.846(8)$		2402.2	4.9%	2576.1	4.9%	2861.7	13.3%	2499.8	1.1%	2525.3	0.063%	2573.6	1.8%

 Table III:5A — ($^{20}\text{Ne-H}^+$) bound states and transitions: comparison between experimental data and various potentials (Mittman, Konrad, G.T., Rosmus, Trial 1, Trial 2).

TABELLA III:5B ($^{40}\text{Ar-H}^+$) STATI LEGATI E TRANSIZIONI

	I: EXPERIM.		II: MITTMAN		III: KONRAD		IV: G.T.		V: ROSMUS		VI: PROVA 1		VII: PROVA 2	
\mathcal{E}	$(4.01 \pm 0.03) \text{ eV}$	4.04 eV	4.05 eV	4.147 eV	4.073 eV	4.03 eV	4.018 eV	4.03 eV	4.03 eV	4.03 eV	4.03 eV	4.018 eV	4.018 eV	4.018 eV
R_e	1.282 \AA	1.31 \AA	1.282 \AA	1.282 \AA	1.274 \AA	1.28 \AA	1.282 \AA	1.274 \AA	1.28 \AA	1.28 \AA	1.28 \AA	1.282 \AA	1.282 \AA	1.282 \AA
	$(E \pm \Delta E) / \text{cm}^{-1}$	$\Delta E/E$	$E(\text{cm}^{-1})$	ΔE_{exp}										
$E(0,0)$	61400 ± 242	0.8%	31281	0.6%	31358	0.8%	32032	3%	31510	1.3%	31160	0.19%	31090	0.03%
$E(1,0)$	28536 ± 242	0.9%	28790	0.9%	28848	1.1%	29397	2.8%	28892	1.3%	28567	0.41%	28533	0.01%
$E(2,0)$	26140 ± 177	0.7%	26406	1.0%	26445	1.2%	26777	2.4%	26398	1%	26095	0.18%	26088	0.20%
$E(3,0)$	23769 ± 177	0.8%	24138	1.6%	24157	1.6%	24358	2.5%	24027	1%	23742	0.12%	23752	0.07%
$E(4,0)$	21495 ± 194	0.9%	21979	2.3%	21977	2.2%	22071	2.7%	21778	1.3%	21506	0.06%	21530	0.16%
$E(5,0)$	19373 ± 210	1.1%	19928	2.9%	19905	2.7%	19911	2.8%	19650	1.4%	19387	0.07%	19373	0.24%
$R(0,4)$	$2680.522(3)$	cm^{-1}	2576.0	3.9%	2598.9	3.0%	2782.8	3.8%	2709.3	1%	2684.2	0.14%	2651.2	1.1%
$R(1,4)$	$2558.182(4)$	cm^{-1}	2465.7	3.6%	2488.3	2.7%	2643.7	3.3%	2581.2	0.9%	2559.7	0.06%	2535.1	0.9%
$R(2,4)$	$2438.772(6)$	cm^{-1}	2346.5	3.8%	2371.1	2.8%	2504.2	2.5%	2454.5	0.65%	2436.8	0.08%	2422.1	0.68%
$R(3,4)$	$2322.157(6)$	cm^{-1}	2234.2	3.8%	2258.9	2.7%	2364.3	1.8%	2329.3	0.3%	2315.7	0.28%	2305.6	0.71%
$R(4,4)$	$2208.158(6)$	cm^{-1}	2124.1	3.8%	2148.5	2.7%	2232.9	1.4%	2205.5	0.12%	2196.1	0.54%	2189.2	0.80%
$R(5,4)$	$2096.534(6)$	cm^{-1}	2014.5	3.9%	2038.3	2.8%	2103.8	0.3%	2083.1	0.65%	2078.1	0.88%	2073.3	1.1%
$R(6,4)$	$1986.993(6)$	cm^{-1}	1906.5	4.1%	1929.1	2.9%	1977.3	0.5%	1962.2	1.25%	1961.4	1.25%	1957.2	1.5%

Table III:5B — ($^{40}\text{Ar-H}^+$) bound states and transitions: comparison between experimental data and various potentials (Mittman, Konrad, G.T., Rosmus, Trial 1, Trial 2).

Tables III:5a and III:5b report, in addition to the bound state energies, for neon the transitions of the fundamental band of ($^{20}\text{Ne-H}^+$) and for argon the transition $R(4)$, chosen as representative, from the 7 known bands of ($^{40}\text{Ar-H}^+$). However, a large discrepancy with the differential cross section measurements is present.

This situation is not specific to potential (III IV.6), but also occurs, for example, for the potential:

$$W(R) = \varepsilon [X^m(\rho) - mX(\rho)] / (m - 1) \quad \text{with } \rho = R/R_e$$

$$X(\rho) = (1/\rho^a) \exp[b(1 - \rho) + c(1 - \rho^2)/2] \quad \text{(III 4.6)}$$

of which potential (III IV.6) is a special case with $m = 2$; some tests carried out on this potential, in which m is treated as a free parameter while ε , R_e , a , b , c are determined as for potential (III IV.6), have shown that for no value of the parameter m is the disagreement with the scattering data improved (we note that m must be greater than 1; for $m = 0$ the potential is identically zero and setting $m < 1$ is equivalent to setting $W[m, a, b, c] \rightarrow W[1/m, ma, mb, mc] = W[m', a', b', c']$ with $m' > 1$). The reasons for this disagreement are indeed of a more general nature.

Before proceeding to illustrate them it is useful to verify the accuracy of three potentials that have been proposed in the literature, together with new experimental data, for describing elastic noble-gas-proton scattering. These are modified potentials, meaning that their analytical form derives from a simple potential model that is modified by allowing the various dimensionless parameters α , β , γ, \dots to take different values before and after R_e ; as is easily seen by writing the potential in reduced form (II IV.2); a change in the values of the dimensionless parameters in the transition from the inner to the outer region (while R_e and ε naturally remain constant) does not entail any discontinuity at $R = R_e$ in the potential (which equals $W_e = -\varepsilon$) or in its first derivative (which vanishes). The discontinuities naturally appear in derivatives above the first.

The parameters of these potentials were ultimately determined by a comparison procedure in which their values were varied and their agreement with the data assessed until it was deemed satisfactory. This method can be considered safer than direct inversion methods, not requiring the approximations demanded by the latter.

The first of the three potentials we shall call the ‘‘Mittman potential’’ (Mittman '71, Mittman '70) and we report the comparison with the scattering data in Figures (III-1) and that with the data on bound states in columns I and II of Table III:5; its analytical form is that of the ‘‘modified Morse potential’’:

$$W(R) = \varepsilon [X^2(\rho) - 2X(\rho)] \quad \text{with } \rho = R/R_e$$

$$X(\rho) = \exp[b(1 - \rho)] \quad \text{with } b = b_1 \text{ for } R < R_e, \quad b = b_2 \text{ for } R > R_e \quad \text{(III 4.2)}$$

where the parameters are reported in the following table:

Table III.6 — Mittman Potential

	ε (eV)	R_e (Å)	b_1	b_2
(Ne-H) ⁺	2.28 ± 0.1	0.99 ± 0.03	2.68	2.78
(Ar-H) ⁺	4.04 ± 0.1	1.31 ± 0.07	2.50	2.15
(Kr-H) ⁺	4.45 ± 0.1	1.47 ± 0.06	2.50	2.00

It can be noted that in addition to having errors of about 5% in Table III.5, the maxima of the cross section calculated at $E = 14.8$ eV are out of phase by about 20 at larger angles (see Figures (III-5)).

For this reason the Mittman potential was taken as a starting point (Konrad '83) for a further parameter optimisation procedure to improve its agreement with the data; the following Table III.7 contains the parameters of the “Konrad potential”:

Fig. III-5A — Differential cross section $H^+ + Ne$ calculated with the MTTMAN potential, compared with experimental data. a) $E_{lab} = 14.8$ eV; b) $E_{cm} = 5.14$ eV; c) $E_{cm} = 1.90$ eV.

Fig. III-5B — Differential cross section $H^+ + Ar$ calculated with the Mittleman potential, compared with experimental data. a) $E_{lab} = 10.7 \text{ eV}$; b) $E_{lab} = 20 \text{ eV}$; c) $E_{lab} = 29.8 \text{ eV}$.

Fig. III-5C — Differential cross section $H^+ + Ar$ calculated with the Mittleman potential, compared with experimental data. a) $E_{cm} = 4.7$ eV; b) $E_{cm} = 5$ eV; c) $E_{lab} = 14.8$ eV.

Table III.7 — Konrad Potential

	ε (eV)	R_e (Å)	b_1	b_2
(Ne-H) ⁺	2.28	0.996	2.70	2.55
(Ar-H) ⁺	4.05	1.282	2.40	2.25

This potential is undoubtedly superior to the Mittman potential both for its better agreement with the bound states and transition energies (columns I and III of Table III:5) and for its agreement with the slow oscillations of the cross sections, as shown in Figures (III 6).

Finally, the potential we shall denote by the abbreviation G.T. (Gianturco and Toennies, see Gianturco '86) is a modified potential whose analytical form is based on potential (III 4.5), which can be regarded as a generalisation of the Morse potential or of the Lennard-Jones LJ(12,6) potential, for example, which are derivable from it as special cases for $a = 0$, $b \neq 0$ and $A = 6$, $b = 0$ respectively. Its form is therefore:

$$W(R) = \varepsilon [X^2(\rho) - 2X(\rho)] \quad \text{with } \rho = R/R_e$$

$$X(\rho) = (1/\rho^a) \exp[b(1 - \rho)] \quad \begin{array}{l} a = a_1, b = b_1 \quad \text{for } R < R_e \\ a = a_2, b = b_2 \quad \text{for } R > R_e \end{array} \quad \text{(III 4.3)}$$

and the parameters are given in Table III.8:

Table III.8 — G.T. Potential

	ε (eV)	R_e (Å)	a_1	a_2	b_1	b_2
(Ne-H) ⁺	2.3	0.996	0.50	0.90	2.35	2.07
(Ar-H) ⁺	4.15	1.282	0.40	0.48	1.82	2.18

Fig. III-6A — Differential cross section $H^+ + Ne$ calculated with the Konrad potential, compared with experimental data. a) $E_{lab} = 14.8 \text{ eV}$; b) $E_{cm} = 5.14 \text{ eV}$; c) $E_{cm} = 1.90 \text{ eV}$.

Fig. III-6B — Differential cross section $H^+ + Ar$ calculated with the Konrad potential, compared with experimental data. a) $E_{lab} = 10.7 \text{ eV}$; b) $E_{lab} = 20 \text{ eV}$; c) $E_{lab} = 29.8 \text{ eV}$.

Fig. III-6C — Differential cross section $H^+ + Ar$ calculated with the Konrad potential, compared with experimental data. a) $E_{cm} = 4.7$ eV; b) $E_{cm} = 5$ eV; c) $E_{lab} = 14.8$ eV.

The comparison in Table III.5 shows errors of the same order of magnitude as those of the Mittman potential, while Figures III.7 show it to be in agreement with all available scattering data.

We can now explain why the “Trial 1” potential of equation (III 4.6) or its gen-

eralisation of equation (III 4.8), which reproduce the bound states so well, fail to reproduce the cross sections. The form of potential (III 4.6), apart from the “modified” parameters, is similar to the analytical form of the G.T. potential, differing from it in the term $c(1 - \rho^2)/2$ in the exponent; as suggested by Figures (III-7), we assume that the correct general form of the potential is that of the G.T. potential, which for $R > R_e$ receives the dominant contribution from the term $-2\varepsilon X(\rho)$, proportional to $(1/\rho_{a_2}) \exp(-b_2\rho)$, while for $R < R_e$ it receives the dominant contribution from $\varepsilon X^2(\rho)$, proportional to $(1/\rho^{2a_1}) \exp(-2b_1\rho)$. The powers of $1/\rho$ and the coefficients of the exponentials that dominate at small and large distances are therefore $2a_1, 2b_1$ and a_2, b_2 respectively. Their ratio, which in the case of $(\text{Ar-H})^+$ is $2a_1/a_2 \cong 1.67$ and $2b_1/b_2 \cong 2.4$, differs for the a 's and the b 's. If instead we use unmodified potentials, these ratios will evidently be equal to each other and equal to 2 or to m depending on whether potential (III 4.6) or its generalisation (III 4.8) is used.

What has been said about this specific example applies to all potentials for which the ratio of the powers and exponentials before and after R_e is the same.

The versatility of the modified potentials now becomes evident: although they do not possess continuous derivatives at $R = R_e$, thus making the theory of Chapter III.2 §3 inapplicable, they allow the representation of very general potentials, with exponential and $1/\rho$ behaviours that are completely independent for $R > R_e$ and for $R < R_e$.

The reasons for the attempt that was made¹ to find a new modified potential can now be understood; taking as a starting point the G.T. potential, which is in agreement with the scattering data but has mean errors of 3–5% on the bound states, the parameters were re-optimised by variation. The resulting potential, which we shall call “Trial 2”, therefore has the same analytical form as the G.T. potential but with the following parameters:

Table III.9 — “Trial 2” Potential

	ε (eV)	R_e (Å)	a_1	a_2	b_1	b_2
$(\text{Ne-H})^+$	2.28	0.996	0.40	0.80	2.15	1.85
$(\text{Ar-H})^+$	4.018	1.282	0.36	0.48	1.72	2.00

¹In collaboration with O. Roncero.

Fig. III-7C — Differential cross section $H^+ + Ar$ calculated with the G.T. potential, compared with experimental data. a) $E_{cm} = 4.7 \text{ eV}$; b) $E_{cm} = 5 \text{ eV}$; c) $E_{lab} = 14.8 \text{ eV}$.

Fig. III-7A — Differential cross section $H^+ + Ne$ calculated with the G.T. potential, compared with experimental data. a) $E_{lab} = 14.8 \text{ eV}$; b) $E_{cm} = 5.14 \text{ eV}$; c) $E_{cm} = 1.90 \text{ eV}$.

Fig. III-7B — Differential cross section $H^+ + Ar$ calculated with the G.T. potential, compared with experimental data. a) $E_{lab} = 10.7 \text{ eV}$; b) $E_{lab} = 20 \text{ eV}$; c) $E_{lab} = 29.8 \text{ eV}$.

Its agreement with the bound states is good (columns I and VI of Table III.2) while the cross sections undergo no substantial changes with respect to those of the G.T. potential (Figure (III-8)). These potentials, together with the G.T. potential for $(\text{Ar-H})^+$, will be used in the study of the energies, widths and photodissociation of resonant states. This study will be carried out both with semiclassical methods and with quantum treatments of the behaviour of the $(\text{R-H})^+$ systems near the resonance energies (see Chapter IV).

Finally, a potential worthy of mention represents the result of the most accurate calculations performed to date on $(\text{R-H})^+$ systems using ab initio methods, that is, by solving the fixed-nucleus equation. We shall refer to it as the “Rosmus potential” (Rosmus '79, Rosmus '80); it was obtained using the SCEP/CEPA method, which provides more accurate results than the conventional SCF or CI methods (Szabo Ch. 5); the quality of the calculations is visible in Table III.5 (columns I and IV). The comparison with the cross sections is complicated, however, by the fact that since the potentials are calculated at only a few points around $R = R_e$, a preliminary interpolation and above all an extrapolation are required, which ultimately remain arbitrary; it is probably for this reason that the agreement is better for neon, calculated over a sufficiently wide region of R , than for argon, calculated at only 8 points (see Figures III.10).

Fig. III-8 — Comparison of the two cross sections at 14.8 eV between the original parameters (G.T.) and the modified parameters (Trial 2) for $(\text{Ne-H})^+$.

FIGURA III-10A

Fig. III-10A — Differential cross section $H^+ + Ne$ calculated with the Rosmus potential, compared with experimental data. a) $E_{lab} = 14.8 \text{ eV}$; b) $E_{cm} = 5.14 \text{ eV}$; c) $E_{cm} = 1.90 \text{ eV}$.

Fig. III-10B — Differential cross section $H^+ + Ar$ calculated with the Rosmus potential, compared with experimental data. a) $E_{lab} = 10.7 \text{ eV}$; b) $E_{lab} = 20 \text{ eV}$; c) $E_{lab} = 29.8 \text{ eV}$.

Fig. III-10C — Differential cross section $H^+ + Ar$ calculated with the Rosmus potential, compared with experimental data. a) $E_{cm} = 4.7 \text{ eV}$; b) $E_{cm} = 5 \text{ eV}$; c) $E_{lab} = 14.8 \text{ eV}$.

Appendix III:

List of Some Available Experimental Data

Data Set III-A1: List of spectroscopic transitions of: $(^{22}\text{Ne-H})^+$, $(^{20}\text{Ne-H})^+$, $(^{40}\text{Ar-H})^+$

(Wong '82, Brault '82, Johns '84, Bowman '83)

Data Set III-A2: Spectra obtained in the experiment on bound state energies.

(Lorenzen '80, Lorenzen '81)

Data Set III-A3: Differential cross sections for Ne-p, Ar-p.

(Mittman '70, Mittman '71, Rich '71, Konrad '83, Gianturco '86)

Data Set III-A4: Spectra obtained in the collision-induced dissociation experiment of $(\text{He-H})^+$ (Shopman '73 and bibliography cited therein)

Data Set III-A5: Spectra obtained in the photodissociation experiment of $(\text{He-H})^+$ (Carrington '81)

III. The Atom-Ion Interaction from Experimental Data

BANDA		$v = 1 \leftrightarrow v = 0$	$^{40}\text{Ar}-\text{H}^+$		$^{40}\text{Ar}-\text{H}^+$			
BANDA			BANDA	$v = 2 \leftrightarrow v = 1$	BANDA	$v = 3 \leftrightarrow v = 2$		
1<-> 0	R(35)	= 2735.5780	2<-> 1	R(33)	= 2625.5660	3<-> 2	R(30)	= 2525.2100
1<-> 0	R(34)	= 2749.2160	2<-> 1	R(32)	= 2637.3100	3<-> 2	R(29)	= 2534.0930
1<-> 0	R(33)	= 2761.7580	2<-> 1	R(31)	= 2647.9740	3<-> 2	R(28)	= 2541.9250
1<-> 0	R(32)	= 2773.2100	2<-> 1	R(30)	= 2657.5700	3<-> 2	R(27)	= 2548.7210
1<-> 0	R(31)	= 2783.5680	2<-> 1	R(29)	= 2666.1040	3<-> 2	R(26)	= 2554.4870
1<-> 0	R(30)	= 2792.8490	2<-> 1	R(28)	= 2673.5810	3<-> 2	R(25)	= 2559.2272
1<-> 0	R(29)	= 2801.0510	2<-> 1	R(27)	= 2680.0080	3<-> 2	R(24)	= 2562.9531
1<-> 0	R(28)	= 2808.1880	2<-> 1	R(26)	= 2685.3950	3<-> 2	R(23)	= 2565.6733
1<-> 0	R(27)	= 2814.2650	2<-> 1	R(25)	= 2689.7452	3<-> 2	R(22)	= 2567.3948
1<-> 0	R(26)	= 2819.2860	2<-> 1	R(24)	= 2693.0717	3<-> 2	R(21)	= 2568.1273
1<-> 0	R(25)	= 2823.2588	2<-> 1	R(23)	= 2695.3793	3<-> 2	R(20)	= 2567.8790
1<-> 0	R(24)	= 2826.1921	2<-> 1	R(22)	= 2696.6761	3<-> 2	R(19)	= 2566.6578
1<-> 0	R(23)	= 2828.0960	2<-> 1	R(21)	= 2696.9727	3<-> 2	R(18)	= 2564.4790
1<-> 0	R(22)	= 2828.9139	2<-> 1	R(20)	= 2696.2766	3<-> 2	R(17)	= 2561.3464
1<-> 0	R(21)	= 2828.8371	2<-> 1	R(19)	= 2694.5936	3<-> 2	R(16)	= 2557.2683
1<-> 0	R(20)	= 2827.6936	2<-> 1	R(18)	= 2691.9377	3<-> 2	R(15)	= 2552.2596
1<-> 0	R(19)	= 2825.5499	2<-> 1	R(17)	= 2688.3159	3<-> 2	R(14)	= 2546.3296
1<-> 0	R(18)	= 2822.4184	2<-> 1	R(16)	= 2683.7529	3<-> 2	R(13)	= 2539.4870
1<-> 0	R(17)	= 2818.3064	2<-> 1	R(15)	= 2678.2148	3<-> 2	R(12)	= 2531.7497
1<-> 0	R(16)	= 2813.2248	2<-> 1	R(14)	= 2671.7561	3<-> 2	R(11)	= 2523.1128
1<-> 0	R(15)	= 2807.1825	2<-> 1	R(13)	= 2664.3716	3<-> 2	R(10)	= 2513.6017
1<-> 0	R(14)	= 2800.1900	2<-> 1	R(12)	= 2656.0729	3<-> 2	R(9)	= 2503.2253
1<-> 0	R(13)	= 2792.2586	2<-> 1	R(11)	= 2646.8723	3<-> 2	R(8)	= 2491.9933
1<-> 0	R(12)	= 2783.3997	2<-> 1	R(10)	= 2636.7799	3<-> 2	R(7)	= 2479.9203
1<-> 0	R(11)	= 2773.6237	2<-> 1	R(9)	= 2625.8078	3<-> 2	R(6)	= 2467.0165
1<-> 0	R(10)	= 2762.9019	2<-> 1	R(8)	= 2613.9682	3<-> 2	R(5)	= 2453.2970
1<-> 0	R(9)	= 2751.3668	2<-> 1	R(7)	= 2601.2729	3<-> 2	R(4)	= 2438.7720
1<-> 0	R(8)	= 2738.9102	2<-> 1	R(6)	= 2587.7351	3<-> 2	R(3)	= 2423.4580
1<-> 0	R(7)	= 2725.5847	2<-> 1	R(5)	= 2573.3661	3<-> 2	R(2)	= 2407.3660
1<-> 0	R(6)	= 2711.4031	2<-> 1	R(4)	= 2558.1824	3<-> 2	R(1)	= 2390.5050
1<-> 0	R(5)	= 2696.3731	2<-> 1	R(3)	= 2542.1941	3<-> 2	P(1)	= 2335.4950
1<-> 0	R(4)	= 2680.5227	2<-> 1	R(2)	= 2525.4144	3<-> 2	P(2)	= 2315.6750
1<-> 0	R(3)	= 2663.8513	2<-> 1	R(1)	= 2507.8607	3<-> 2	P(3)	= 2295.2590
1<-> 0	R(2)	= 2646.3774	2<-> 1	R(0)	= 2489.5495	3<-> 2	P(4)	= 2274.1170
1<-> 0	R(1)	= 2628.1149	2<-> 1	P(1)	= 2450.6810	3<-> 2	P(5)	= 2252.3140
1<-> 0	R(0)	= 2609.0767	2<-> 1	P(2)	= 2430.1672	3<-> 2	P(6)	= 2229.8620
1<-> 0	P(1)	= 2568.7357	2<-> 1	P(3)	= 2408.9480	3<-> 2	P(7)	= 2206.7770
1<-> 0	P(2)	= 2547.4635	2<-> 1	P(4)	= 2387.0393	3<-> 2	P(8)	= 2183.0740
1<-> 0	P(3)	= 2525.4749	2<-> 1	P(5)	= 2364.4568	3<-> 2	P(9)	= 2158.7720
1<-> 0	P(4)	= 2502.7856	2<-> 1	P(6)	= 2341.2155	3<-> 2	P(10)	= 2133.8840
1<-> 0	P(5)	= 2479.4113	2<-> 1	P(7)	= 2317.3322	3<-> 2	P(11)	= 2108.4260
1<-> 0	P(6)	= 2455.3682	2<-> 1	P(8)	= 2292.8210	3<-> 2	P(12)	= 2082.4120
1<-> 0	P(7)	= 2430.6705	2<-> 1	P(9)	= 2267.6984	3<-> 2	P(13)	= 2055.8580
1<-> 0	P(8)	= 2405.3358	2<-> 1	P(10)	= 2241.9795	3<-> 2	P(14)	= 2028.7810
1<-> 0	P(9)	= 2379.3788	2<-> 1	P(11)	= 2215.6788	3<-> 2	P(15)	= 2001.1970
1<-> 0	P(10)	= 2352.8151	2<-> 1	P(12)	= 2188.8181	3<-> 2	P(16)	= 1973.1200
1<-> 0	P(11)	= 2325.6623	2<-> 1	P(13)	= 2161.4084	3<-> 2	P(17)	= 1944.5650
1<-> 0	P(12)	= 2297.9348	2<-> 1	P(14)	= 2133.4645	3<-> 2	P(18)	= 1915.5570
1<-> 0	P(13)	= 2269.6506	2<-> 1	P(15)	= 2105.0061	3<-> 2	P(19)	= 1886.0990
1<-> 0	P(14)	= 2240.8247	2<-> 1	P(16)	= 2076.0465	3<-> 2	P(20)	= 1856.2150
1<-> 0	P(15)	= 2211.4604	2<-> 1	P(17)	= 2046.6047			
1<-> 0	P(16)	= 2181.6130	2<-> 1	P(18)	= 2016.6926			
1<-> 0	P(17)	= 2151.2637	2<-> 1	P(19)	= 1986.3301			
1<-> 0	P(18)	= 2120.4325	2<-> 1	P(20)	= 1955.5338			
1<-> 0	P(19)	= 2089.1439	2<-> 1	P(21)	= 1924.3130			
1<-> 0	P(20)	= 2057.4126	2<-> 1	P(22)	= 1892.6700			
1<-> 0	P(21)	= 2025.2550	2<-> 1	P(23)	= 1860.6810			
1<-> 0	P(22)	= 1992.6840						
1<-> 0	P(23)	= 1959.7210						
1<-> 0	P(24)	= 1926.3770						
1<-> 0	P(25)	= 1892.6700						
1<-> 0	P(26)	= 1858.6160						
1<-> 0	P(27)	= 1824.2170						

A1

Data Set III A1 — Spectroscopic transitions of $(^{40}\text{Ar}-\text{H})^+$: bands $v = 1 \leftrightarrow 0$, $v = 2 \leftrightarrow 1$, $v = 3 \leftrightarrow 2$.

III. The Atom-Ion Interaction from Experimental Data

$^{40}\text{Ar}-\text{H}^+$		$^{40}\text{Ar}-\text{H}^+$		$^{40}\text{Ar}-\text{H}^+$	
BANDA	$v = 4 \leftrightarrow v = 3$	BANDA	$v = 5 \leftrightarrow v = 4$	BANDA	$v = 6 \leftrightarrow v = 5$
4<-> 3	R(27) = 2420.1280	5<-> 4	R(24) = 2310.6920	6<-> 5	R(19) = 2198.70
4<-> 3	R(26) = 2426.2960	5<-> 4	R(23) = 2314.3040	6<-> 5	R(18) = 2198.02
4<-> 3	R(25) = 2431.4510	5<-> 4	R(22) = 2316.9310	6<-> 5	R(17) = 2196.42
4<-> 3	R(24) = 2435.6000	5<-> 4	R(21) = 2318.5810	6<-> 5	R(16) = 2193.90
4<-> 3	R(23) = 2438.7470	5<-> 4	R(20) = 2319.2740	6<-> 5	R(15) = 2190.47
4<-> 3	R(22) = 2440.9110	5<-> 4	R(19) = 2319.0120	6<-> 5	R(14) = 2186.16
4<-> 3	R(21) = 2442.0890	5<-> 4	R(18) = 2317.8080	6<-> 5	R(13) = 2180.91
4<-> 3	R(20) = 2442.3010	5<-> 4	R(17) = 2315.6750	6<-> 5	R(12) = 2174.91
4<-> 3	R(19) = 2441.5530	5<-> 4	R(16) = 2312.6300	6<-> 5	R(11) = 2167.91
4<-> 3	R(18) = 2439.8530	5<-> 4	R(15) = 2308.6530	6<-> 5	R(10) = 2160.2
4<-> 3	R(17) = 2437.2130	5<-> 4	R(14) = 2303.7870	6<-> 5	R(9) = 2151.18
4<-> 3	R(16) = 2433.6410	5<-> 4	R(13) = 2298.0340	6<-> 5	R(8) = 2142.15
4<-> 3	R(15) = 2429.1500	5<-> 4	R(12) = 2291.4020	6<-> 5	R(7) = 2131.96
4<-> 3	R(14) = 2423.7480	5<-> 4	R(11) = 2283.9030	6<-> 5	R(6) = 2120.92
4<-> 3	R(13) = 2417.4480	5<-> 4	R(10) = 2275.5500	6<-> 5	R(5) = 2096.52
4<-> 3	R(12) = 2410.2580	5<-> 4	R(9) = 2266.3540	6<-> 5	P(3) = 1979.76
4<-> 3	R(11) = 2402.1910	5<-> 4	R(8) = 2256.3280	6<-> 5	P(4) = 1950.77
4<-> 3	R(10) = 2393.2590	5<-> 4	R(7) = 2245.4810	6<-> 5	P(5) = 1931.22
4<-> 3	R(9) = 2383.4730	5<-> 4	R(6) = 2233.8300	6<-> 5	P(6) = 1911.04
4<-> 3	R(8) = 2372.8440	5<-> 4	R(5) = 2221.3830	6<-> 5	P(7) = 1890.22
4<-> 3	R(7) = 2361.3860	5<-> 4	R(4) = 2208.1580	6<-> 5	P(8) = 1868.88
4<-> 3	R(6) = 2349.1110	5<-> 4	P(5) = 2035.8970	6<-> 5	P(9) = 1846.95
4<-> 3	R(5) = 2336.0310	5<-> 4	P(6) = 2014.9770		
4<-> 3	R(4) = 2322.1570	5<-> 4	P(7) = 1993.4500		
4<-> 3	R(3) = 2307.5070	5<-> 4	P(9) = 1948.5990		
4<-> 3	R(2) = 2292.0850	5<-> 4	P(10) = 1925.3230		
4<-> 3	R(1) = 2275.9190	5<-> 4	P(11) = 1901.4870		
4<-> 3	P(3) = 2184.2750	5<-> 4	P(12) = 1877.1150		
4<-> 3	P(4) = 2163.8940				
4<-> 3	P(5) = 2142.8510				
4<-> 3	P(6) = 2121.1730				
4<-> 3	P(7) = 2098.8720				
4<-> 3	P(8) = 2075.9700				
4<-> 3	P(9) = 2052.4680				
4<-> 3	P(10) = 2028.3930				
4<-> 3	P(11) = 2003.7550				
4<-> 3	P(12) = 1978.5850				
4<-> 3	P(13) = 1952.8540				
4<-> 3	P(14) = 1926.6300				
4<-> 3	P(15) = 1899.8980				
4<-> 3	P(16) = 1872.6800				
4<-> 3	P(17) = 1844.9760				

$^{40}\text{Ar}-\text{H}^+$		$^{40}\text{Ar}-\text{H}^+$	
BANDA	$v = 7 \leftrightarrow v = 6$	BANDA	$v = 6 \leftrightarrow v = 5$
7<-> 6	R(9) = 2038.9020	6<-> 5	R(19) = 2198.70
7<-> 6	R(8) = 2030.1020	6<-> 5	R(18) = 2198.02
7<-> 6	R(7) = 2020.5040	6<-> 5	R(17) = 2196.42
7<-> 6	R(6) = 2010.1050	6<-> 5	R(16) = 2193.90
7<-> 6	R(5) = 1998.9200	6<-> 5	R(15) = 2190.47
7<-> 6	R(4) = 1986.9930	6<-> 5	R(14) = 2186.16

$^{20}\text{Ne}-\text{H}^+$		$^{22}\text{Ne}-\text{H}^+$	
BANDA	$v = 1 \leftrightarrow v = 0$	BANDA	$v = 1 \leftrightarrow v = 0$
1<-> 0	R(6) = 2856.3412	1<-> 0	R(6) = -
1<-> 0	R(5) = 2838.1535	1<-> 0	R(5) = -
1<-> 0	R(4) = 2817.4273	1<-> 0	R(4) = 2811.5467
1<-> 0	R(3) = 2794.2240	1<-> 0	R(3) = 2788.4168
1<-> 0	R(2) = 2768.6034	1<-> 0	R(2) = 2762.8834
1<-> 0	R(1) = 2740.6262	1<-> 0	R(1) = 2735.0111
1<-> 0	R(0) = 2710.3557	1<-> 0	R(0) = 2704.8620
1<-> 0	P(1) = 2643.1910	1<-> 0	P(1) = 2637.4815
1<-> 0	P(2) = 2606.4239	1<-> 0	P(2) = 2601.3746
1<-> 0	P(3) = 2567.6203	1<-> 0	P(3) = 2562.7479
1<-> 0	P(4) = 2526.8468	1<-> 0	P(4) = -

A1

Data Set III A1 — Spectroscopic transitions of $(^{40}\text{Ar}-\text{H})^+$: bands $v = 4 \leftrightarrow 3$ through $v = 7 \leftrightarrow 6$; and of $(^{20}\text{Ne}-\text{H})^+$ and $(^{22}\text{Ne}-\text{H})^+$: band $v = 1 \leftrightarrow 0$.

A2: SPETTRI DELLE ENERGIE DEGLI STATI LEGATI (LORENZEN '80)

Data Set III A2 — Bound state energy spectra (Lorenzen '80). Top: $\text{Ne}(^3P_2) + \text{H} \rightarrow \text{NeH}^+(^1\Sigma^+, v, J) + e^-$. Bottom: $\text{Ar}(^3P_2) + \text{H} \rightarrow \text{ArH}^+(^1\Sigma^+, v, J) + e^-$.

III. The Atom-Ion Interaction from Experimental Data

Data Set III A3 — Experimental differential cross sections $H^+ + Ne$. a) $E_{lab} = 14.8$ eV (Gianturco '86); b) $E_{cm} = 5.14$ eV (Konrad '83); c) $E_{cm} = 1.90$ eV (Konrad '83).

Data Set III A3 — Experimental differential cross sections $H^+ + Ar$. a) $E_{cm} = 4.7$ eV (Konrad '83); b) $E_{cm} = 5$ eV (Rich '71); c) $E_{lab} = 14.8$ eV (Gianturco '86).

Data Set III A3 — Experimental differential cross sections $H^+ + Ar$ (continued).
 a) $E_{lab} = 10.7$ eV (Mittman '70); b) $E_{lab} = 20$ eV (Mittman '70); c) $E_{lab} = 29.8$ eV (Mittman '70).

III. The Atom-Ion Interaction from Experimental Data

A-4 : SPETTRI OTTENUTI NELL'ESPERIENZA SULLA DISSOCIAZIONE
DELL' (He-H)⁺. (Shopman '70, Shopman '73)

Data Set III A4 — Spectra obtained in the collision-induced dissociation experiment of (He-H)⁺ (Shopman '70, Shopman '73).

A5 : SPETTRI OTTENUTI NELLA ESPERIENZA
 SULLA FOTODISSOCIAZIONE DELL' $(\text{He-H})^+$.
 (CARRINGTON '81)

Data Set III A5 — Spectra obtained in the photodissociation experiment of $(\text{He-H})^+$ (Carrington '81). (a) transition $7,11 \leftarrow 5,12$; (b) transition $6,13 \leftarrow 5,12$.

Chapter IV — Molecular Resonances and Photodissociation

Chapter IV 1: General Definitions

In this chapter we shall treat resonant states, those angular-momentum eigenstates with positive energy that are distinguished from all other states of the continuum spectrum by certain peculiar characteristics.

These characteristics occur in different phenomena that give rise to different definitions of resonance; while there is thus no single definition of resonance, the various definitions are in substantial agreement with one another and it is possible to speak in general of “resonances” without causing confusion.

Among the most noteworthy phenomena reported as evidence for the existence of resonances are: a) scattering experiments, in which at a certain energy E^* the two colliding particles show a marked increase in the intensity of mutual interaction and a tendency to bind to one another in a single system (with finite mean lifetime); b) electromagnetic transitions from a bound state to a continuum state, which are particularly favoured if the final state has energy $E \cong E^*$ and which can lead to dissociation of the molecule.

A theoretical definition of resonance can be formulated within the semiclassical framework through the “time delay function” $\tau_J(E)$, defined as the finite time obtained as the difference between the duration of the collision between the two particles and the duration the “collision” would have if the two particles did not interact ($W(R) \equiv 0$), durations which, taken individually, would be infinite. It can be expressed through a simple relation connecting it to the (semiclassical) phase shift $\delta_J(E)$:

$$\tau_J(E) = 2\hbar(\partial\delta_J/\partial E) \quad (\text{IV 1.1})$$

An intuitive interpretation of (IV 1.1) can be given by considering the definition of the classical time delay function $\tau(E, L)$ (where $L = bP$ is the classical orbital

angular momentum):

$$\tau(E, L) = \int_r^\infty dR/V(R) - \int_b^\infty dR/V_0(R) \quad (\text{IV } 1.2)$$

where $V(R) = \sqrt{[2(E - W(R) - L^2/R^2)/M]}$ and $V_0(R) = \sqrt{[2(E - L^2/R^2)/M]}$; if we denote by ΔS the difference between the classical asymptotic actions in the presence and absence of interaction:

$$\Delta S = S - S_0 = \int_r^\infty p(R) dR - \int_b^\infty p_0(R) dR \quad (\text{IV } 1.3)$$

then τ appears to be the variable conjugate to E and is given by:

$$\tau_J(E) = \partial\Delta S/\partial E \quad (\text{IV } 1.4)$$

It can be noted that the variable conjugate to L is instead the deflection function $\Theta(b)$:

$$\Theta(b) = \partial\Delta S/\partial L \quad (\text{IV } 1.5)$$

The correspondence with classical mechanics is established by setting $\Psi \cong e^{iS/\hbar}$; noting that a single partial wave of angular momentum J has as its asymptotic limit (Chapter II 2, §2):

$$\Psi_J \rightarrow (1/2ik)f_J \exp[i(2\delta_J + kR)] \quad (\text{IV } 1.6)$$

one finds that $2\delta_J + kR - \pi/2 \cong S/\hbar$ and hence $2\hbar\delta_J \cong S - (kR - \pi/2)\hbar$, that is, it equals the difference between the action S and the action $S_0 = (kR - \pi/2)\hbar$ of a free particle, which coincides with ΔS in the semiclassical approximation.

Despite its dynamical significance, $\tau_J(E)$ can be expressed in terms of the radial part of the stationary eigenfunction $\Psi_{EJ}(R)$ and its asymptotic limit $\Psi_{EJ}^\infty(R) = \sqrt{[2M/\pi\hbar^2k]} \sin\{kR - J\pi/2 + \delta_J(E)\}$ in the following way:

$$\tau_J(E) = \int_0^\infty \{|\Psi_{EJ}(kR)|^2 - |\Psi_{EJ}^\infty(kR)|^2\} dR + (M/\hbar k^2) \sin[2\delta_J(E) - J\pi] \quad (\text{IV } 1.7)$$

This function, in the vicinity of certain critical energy values E^* , exhibits a marked increase that signals the presence of a resonance.

In this case, as in the definitions that follow, the resonance is not identified by the single value E^* , but by a peak centred at E^* ; it is not possible to associate a single energy with the resonance, but it is the resonance that, by definition, is associated with those values of E that cause a visible increase in $\tau_J(E)$; these are all

the values lying in the range of E over which the peak arises. Thus even when one commonly speaks of a resonant state or “quasi-bound state” with energy E^* , what is meant is the “resonance phenomenon” that occurs in the vicinity of E^* , where the peak has its maximum. The width of the peak Γ is related to the mean lifetime of the resonant state through the uncertainty principle and it can be shown (see Le Roy '71) that in this case it is given by:

$$\Gamma = 4\hbar/\tau_J(E^*) \quad (\text{IV } 1.8)$$

Although semiclassical, the definition of resonance through the time delay function $\tau_J(E)$ is connected with the “quantum” definition, which identifies a resonance by studying the behaviour, as a function of energy E , of the partial cross section σ_J :

$$\sigma_J(E) = (4\pi/k^2)(2J+1)[\sin(\delta_J(E))]^2 \quad (\text{IV } 1.9)$$

where $k^2 = 2ME$ with M and E in a.u. In this case the presence of a resonance manifests as a rapid variation of σ_J caused in turn by a rapid variation of δ_J ; if the reference energy of the resonance is taken as the value of E at which the variation becomes fastest, it coincides to good approximation with the value of E at which the variation of δ_J becomes fastest, and for which therefore $\partial\delta_J/\partial E$, i.e. $\tau_J(E)$ in the semiclassical approximation, exhibits a maximum.

The study of the partial cross section is one of the methods used in Chapter IV-2 to determine the position and width of the resonances. The width in this case is estimated as that value Γ for which:

$$\sigma_J(E^* \pm \frac{\Gamma}{2}) = (1/2)\sigma_J(E^*) \quad (\text{IV } 1.10)$$

We now turn to a definition of resonance that studies instead the behaviour of the wave function inside the centrifugal barrier as a function of energy.

As a critical energy value E^* is approached, the wave function shows a remarkable increase in its amplitude (for fixed amplitude of the outer part of the wave function), without the positions of the nodes being appreciably perturbed. This suggests writing the JWKB wave function between the two turning points A and B (see Figure (IV-1)) in the following way (Le Roy '71):

RAPPRESENTAZIONE DEL COMPORAMENTO DELLA FUNZIONE D'ONDA INTERNA
 IN PROSSIMITA' DI UNA RISONANZA DI ENERGIA E^* .

FIGURA IV-1

Fig. IV-1 — Representation of the behaviour of the inner wave function in the vicinity of a resonance of energy E^* . The turning points A and B are indicated on the R axis; F is the asymptotic region.

$$\Psi_{EJ}(R) = \sqrt{[\Lambda_J(E)/K_J(R)]} \cos\left[\int_a^R K_J(r) dr - \pi/4\right] \quad (\text{IV } 1.11)$$

where $\Lambda_J(E)$ is the “inner amplitude function” which presents a maximum at a resonant state and is calculable semiclassically.

The introduction of resonances through the function $\Lambda_J(E)$ is particularly useful for understanding the phenomenon of resonant predissociation, which occurs due to an electromagnetic transition from a bound state to a quasi-bound state. It is indeed clear that the transition from a bound state to a continuum state, whose amplitude is proportional to the matrix element:

$$\langle nJ|D(R)|EJ' \rangle = \int dR \Psi_{nJ}(R) D(R) \Psi_{EJ'}(R) \quad (\text{IV } 1.12)$$

(D is the molecular dipole moment, described in greater detail in Chapter IV 3,§3) will be enormously enhanced for $E \cong E^*$, the energy value at which the overlap of the two wave functions will give the largest contribution to integral (IV 1.12).

* * *

The quasi-bound state definitions presented so far, however, exhibit, in numerical calculations, a substantial difference from the calculation of the eigenvalues of bound states. Indeed, no optimisation technique is available for finding the values E^* of the resonant states of the type described at the end of Chapter II 1.

To find a resonance it is necessary to repeat the same calculation, of $\tau_J(E)$, $\Lambda_J(E)$ or $\sigma_J(E)$, for many values of E , until a structure identifiable as a resonance is found; it should be noted that the number of energies at which the calculation must be repeated can become enormous if the resonance is very narrow and no good initial estimate is available.

For this reason, various semiclassical methods have been proposed that define the resonance through boundary conditions, for which an optimisation method for finding the “eigenvalues of quasi-bound states” can be readily implemented. Once the resonances have been located with such techniques, one can proceed to a calculation based on a different definition of resonance, in order to obtain a more precise estimate or a verification of the correctness of the values E^* found, using the resonance energies and corresponding widths found with the boundary-condition method as the initial estimate.

Among the various boundary-condition methods that have been proposed, the one that has proved most consistent with the other definitions (which are in substantial mutual agreement) is the Airy function boundary-condition method (Le Roy '78, Le Roy '71), which is used by our program to find the resonances. The method uses the theory of the inner amplitude function $\Lambda_J(E)$ and seeks the conditions under which it presents a maximum.

In the vicinity of the 2nd and 3rd turning points, B and C (see Figure (IV-2)), the effective potential $W_J(R) = W(R) + J(J+1)\hbar^2/2mR^2$ can be approximated as:

$$W_J(R) \cong W_J^\circ - F \times (R - R^\circ) \quad (\text{IV } 1.13)$$

where $F = -[\partial W_J/\partial R]$ evaluated at $R = R^\circ$, with R° equal to one of the two outer turning points B or C . The radial Schrödinger equation near one of these points then becomes:

$$[-(\partial_R)^2 - F \times (R - R^\circ)](R\Psi_{EJ}) = (E - W^\circ)(R\Psi_{EJ}) \quad (\text{IV } 1.14)$$

whose general solution is a linear combination of the Airy functions of the first and second kind $\text{Ai}(-z)$ and $\text{Bi}(-z)$:

$$R\Psi_{EJ}(R) = \alpha_1 \text{Ai}(-z) + \alpha_2 \text{Bi}(-z) \quad (\text{IV } 1.15)$$

$$\text{Ai}(-z) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \left[\cos(\xi^3/3 - 2\xi) \right] d\xi \quad (\text{IV } 1.16a)$$

$$\text{Bi}(-z) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \left[e^{-\xi^3/3 - 2\xi} + \sinh(\xi^3/3 - 2\xi) \right] d\xi \quad (\text{IV } 1.16b)$$

where the variable z is defined by the relation:

$$z^{3/2} = (3/2) \int_C^R K_J(r) dr \quad (\text{IV } 1.17)$$

for the outermost turning point, and by an analogous relation (with C replaced by B) for the 2nd turning point. If continuity conditions are imposed between the inner function and the function around the second turning point B , and the same is done between the functions around the 2nd and 3rd turning points B and C (see Figure (IV-2)), it can be shown (see Le Roy '78) that the inner function $\Lambda_J(E)$

LE VARIE FUNZIONI D'ONDA USATE NEL METODO DELLA CONDIZIONE AL
 CONTORNO DELLA FUNZIONE DI AIRY.

FIGURA IV-2

Fig. IV-2 — The various wave functions used in the Airy function boundary-condition method. The turning points A , B and C are indicated, together with the regions of applicability of the WKB approximation and the Airy functions around points B and C .

presents a maximum if the coefficient α_1 of equation (IV 1.15) for the wave

function just beyond the third turning point C vanishes:

$$\alpha_1 = 0 \tag{IV 1.18}$$

With this simple boundary condition all the resonances lying below the maximum of the centrifugal barrier can be found in times of the order of those required to find the bound states.

This semiclassical definition of a resonant state allows the assignment of a vibrational quantum number in a manner analogous to that for bound states, following exactly the same criterion: the vibrational quantum number corresponds to the number of nodes of the radial wave function. According to this procedure, semiclassical resonant states look very similar to bound states. The vibrational quantum numbers appearing in the resonance tables on the following pages are to be understood in this sense.

The width Γ of the resonance is calculated using a formula that essentially represents a modification (see Connor '81) of the semiclassical formula (IV 1.1), where the phase shift $\delta_J(E)$ is calculated semiclassically.

Chapter IV 2: Energies and Widths of Resonances

In this chapter the results of the calculations of the widths and energies of the resonant states, carried out using the potentials selected in Chapter III 4, will be presented.

The intention is to provide estimates of the mean lifetimes and energies of the quasi-bound states of protonated noble gases that could be used in the future for a correct interpretation of the resonance structures observable in experiments, similar to that which we are about to briefly describe, that have already been carried out for $(\text{He-H})^+$.

For light ions such as H_2^+ and $(\text{He-H})^+$, the results of measurements of the positive energies of some resonant states have indeed been available for several years (see for example Shopman '70, Shopman '73). These experiments, for which interpretation was first attempted through various mechanisms of electronic excitation of the molecule, instead required an explanation based on the excitation of the molecule, on the same ground electronic curve, from a bound state to a quasi-bound state, according to the following reaction:

In these experiments a beam of ionised molecules is accelerated by an electrostatic potential of the order of a few kV, then collimated and energy-selected, as illustrated in the schematic of Figure (9-1). The beam then enters a chamber C where the molecules are excited by collision with the contents of the chamber. From that point on, if the excitation has occurred to a quasi-bound state, dissociation may take place in a manner depending on the mean lifetime of the excited state.

The H^+ fragments formed in the first section d of Figure (9-1) are then velocity-selected with a magnetic selector, and the intensity of the fragment beam is studied as a function of its momentum, adjustable by varying the magnetic field of the selector. At the end of the flight path a detector measures the energy and number of arriving H^+ ions. We now see how dissociation via a transition from a discrete state to a continuum state is able to account for the observed spectra, reported in the Appendix to Chapter III.

Fig. IV-3 — Schematic of the experiment on dissociation of $(\text{He-H})^+$ (Shopman '73): source, slits, accelerating plates, collision chamber C , velocity selector, detector. The distance d indicates the path between the collision chamber and the magnetic deflector.

If we denote by E the energy of the resonant state, after the dissociation that occurs by tunnelling under the centrifugal barrier, it will equal the kinetic energy of the fragments in their centre of mass:

$$E = P^2/2M_A + P^2/2M_B \equiv P^2/2M \quad (\text{IV } 2.2)$$

where M_A and M_B denote the masses of the two fragments. The velocity of fragment A (which we shall take to be H^+) is therefore:

$$V_A = P/M_A = \sqrt{(2ME)}/M_A \quad (\text{IV } 2.3)$$

and, denoting by v_b the velocity of the centre of mass of the molecule, whose kinetic energy coincides in practice with the energy eU acquired by traversing the accelerating electrostatic field, the kinetic energy K_A of fragment A in the laboratory reference frame will be:

$$K_A = (1/2)M_A(v_b + V_A)^2 = (1/2)M_Av_b^2 + (1/2)M_AV_A^2 + M_A|v_b||V_A|\cos\theta \quad (\text{IV } 2.4)$$

where $\cos\theta = \cos(v_b, V_A)$; the second term, of the order of eV, is negligible compared with the first, which can be rewritten as:

$$(M_A/2)v_b^2 = [M_A/(M_A+M_B)]\{(1/2)(M_A+M_B)v_b^2\} = M_AeU/(M_A+M_B) \quad (\text{IV } 2.5)$$

and which is therefore of the order of thousands of eV.

Furthermore, all fragments produced by dissociations occurring at angle $\theta \neq 0$ leave the trajectory of the main beam and cannot be detected; only dissociations with $\cos\theta = \pm 1$ reach the detector, and equation (IV 2.4) reads:

$$K_A \cong M_AeU/(M_A + M_B) \pm v_b\sqrt{(2ME)} \quad (\text{IV } 2.6)$$

The largest contributions to the beam intensity will come from those values of E close to the resonance values E^* ; the spectrum of fragment intensity, studied as a function of the energy K_A , should then show, in accordance with equation (IV 2.6), a structure centred around the value $K_A^0 = M_AeU/(M_A + M_B)$ given by the first term of equation (9.6), and present a symmetric structure at those values $E = E^*$ that are the energies of the quasi-bound states.

Some examples of the above spectrum obtained from the dissociation of $(\text{He-H})^+$ are reported in the Appendix to Chapter III.

It should be noted that the dimensions of the apparatus impose restrictions on the resonances that can be detected: if the ion in the resonant state does not dissociate before reaching the magnetic deflector, the H^+ fragment is not detected; the following condition is therefore obtained:

$$v_b\tau < d \quad (\text{IV } 2.7)$$

Setting d (see Figure (IV-3)) $\cong 10$ m, $v_b = \sqrt{(2eU/(M_A + M_B))}$, one finds that with $eU \cong 10$ kV, $v_b \cong 300$ km/s, and hence the following conditions on the mean lifetime τ and width $\Gamma \cong \hbar/\tau$:

$$\tau \lesssim 0.3 \mu\text{s} \quad (\text{IV 2.8a})$$

$$\Gamma \gtrsim 1.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^{-1} \quad (\text{IV 2.8b})$$

We therefore report, in Tables IV:1a and IV:1b, the list of resonances of (Ne-H)⁺ and of (Ar-H)⁺ with $10^{-5} \text{ cm}^{-1} < \Gamma < 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The quantum numbers v and J in the 1st column are to be understood as the number of nodes of the resonant wave function and the angular momentum quantum number. In the 2nd and 3rd columns the energies E_{sc} and widths Γ_{sc} calculated with the semiclassical Airy function boundary-condition method described in Chapter IV 3 are reported. In the last two columns, for comparison, the energies E_Q and widths Γ_Q calculated by studying the behaviour of the partial cross section $\sigma_J(E)$ in the vicinity of the resonance energy are reported for some of the resonances, taking for E_Q the value of the energy at which $\sigma_J(E) = \text{Maximum}$ and for Γ_Q the value such that $\sigma_J(E_Q \pm \frac{\Gamma_Q}{2}) = (1/2)\sigma_J(E_Q)$.

As can be concluded from the comparison of the semiclassical (SC) quantities with the quantum (Q) ones, the Airy function method is consistent, to within cm^{-1} , with the method that uses σ_J .

To show an example of the arrangement of these resonances in the effective potential, Figures (IV-4a) and (IV-4b) display the resonances for some given values of the angular momentum. In Figures (IV-5 ...) and (IV-6a,b) are reported the

TABELLA IV-1 A				
RISONANZE (Ne-H) ⁺ CON $10^{-5} \text{ cm}^{-1} \leq \Gamma \leq 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$				
V, J	$E_{s.c.} (\text{cm}^{-1})$	$\Gamma_{s.c.} (\text{cm}^{-1})$	$E_Q (\text{cm}^{-1})$	$\Gamma_Q (\text{cm}^{-1})$
2, 35	2473.0	6.25	2474.3	6.44
8, 20	474.4	11.42		
7, 23	717.8	9.16	715.7	12.0
1, 37	2940.3	3.91	2941.1	3.81
5, 28	1219.3	2.67	1219.2	3.28
10, 13	102.6	4.97		
0, 39	3501.0	1.71	3501.5	2.22
11, 10	37.2	2.55		
4, 30	1420.2	0.505	1420.5	0.555
13, 5	2.8863	0.80215		
6, 25	794.877	0.4571	795.152	0.460
3, 32	1672.717	0.11708	1673.201	0.12
9, 16	179.482	0.483		
7, 22	491.53	0.118	491.894	0.114
2, 34	1985.0340	0.03205	1985.614	0.032
8, 19	295.5349	0.0910	295.754	0.094
5, 27	894.114	0.0199	894.483	0.0204
1, 36	2367.5475	0.00974	2368.232	0.011
12, 7	5.5957	0.0283	5.515	0.033
0, 38	2833.4690	0.00255	2834.2705	0.0028
4, 29	1031.5052	0.001167	1032.0455	0.00136
6, 24	506.60034	0.00037	506.9249	0.0005
3, 31	1214.20307	0.000107	1214.72276	0.00012
2, 33	1450.03785	0.0000143	1450.64688	0.000024

Table IV-1A — Resonances of (Ne-H)⁺ with $10^{-5} \text{ cm}^{-1} \leq \Gamma \leq 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$: quantum numbers (v, J), energy $E_{s.c.}$ and width $\Gamma_{s.c.}$ (semiclassical method), E_Q and Γ_Q (partial cross section).

TABELLA IV-1B				
RISONANZE DELL'($^{40}\text{Ar-H}$) ⁺				
V, J	$E_{s.c.} (\text{cm}^{-1})$	$\Gamma_{s.c.} (\text{cm}^{-1})$	$E_Q (\text{cm}^{-1})$	$\Gamma_Q (\text{cm}^{-1})$
4, 60	3066.83045	$6.871 \cdot 10^{-5}$		
5, 58	2753.06750	$1.726 \cdot 10^{-5}$		
13, 40	277, 20353	$1.835 \cdot 10^{-5}$		
15, 35	494.02197	$2.199 \cdot 10^{-5}$		
24, 9	1.6453	$3.283 \cdot 10^{-5}$		
19, 24	131.75215	$3.3287 \cdot 10^{-5}$		
6, 56	2474.37106	$4.945 \cdot 10^{-5}$		
18, 27	208.30141	$7.698 \cdot 10^{-5}$		
20, 21	84.67786	0.000105		
11, 45	1207.47908	0.0001179		
0, 69	5408.2897	0.000123	5409.6589	0.00016
7, 54	2227.2742	0.000164	2228.0654	0.000176
17, 30	320.75359	0.000446		
1, 67	4876.43596	0.000513	4877.6980	0.0005
8, 52	2008.3666	0.0006657		
14, 38	724.73863	0.000911		
2, 65	4395.71141	0.00133	4396.8744	0.0015
12, 43	1103.1938	0.00177		
3, 63	3961.9958	0.00299	3963.0664	0.0032
9, 50	1814.4551	0.00318		
16, 33	474.5581	0.00370	474.8540	0.0030
21, 18	58.1738	0.00581		

Table IV-1B — Resonances of ($^{40}\text{Ar-H}$)⁺: first part (very small widths).

v	J	$E_{s.c.} (cm^{-1})$	$\Gamma_{s.c.} (cm^{-1})$	$E_{Q.} (cm^{-1})$	$\Gamma_{Q.} (cm^{-1})$
4	61	3571.4748	0.00656	3572.4565	0.0069
5	59	3220.51982	0.0150	3221.418	0.0350
10	48	1642.46562	0.0181		
25	7	1.55253	0.02514		
13	41	1009.6912	0.0028		
15	36	674.043	0.0349	674.357	0.041
0	70	6052.7766	0.0358	6054.114	0.042
6	57	2905.5596	0.0373	2906.379	0.038
23	12	13.5423	0.0498		
7	55	2622.9766	0.1018		
11	46	1488.9187	0.1173		
1	68	5474.9607	0.1358	5476.160	0.132
18	28	318.464	0.145		
19	25	222.140	0.175		
17	31	450.148	0.259		
22	15	36.633	0.277		
8	53	2369.075	0.305		
2	66	4951.063	0.317	4952.176	0.207
14	39	921.934	0.381		
3	64	4476.282	0.622	4477.376	0.672
20	22	154.770	0.625		
16	34	621.597	0.760		
12	44	1349.289	0.773		
9	51	2140.072	0.9804		

Table IV-1B — Resonances of $(^{40}\text{Ar-H})^+$: continuation.

V, J	$E_{s.c.} (cm^{-1})$	$\Gamma_{s.c.} (cm^{-1})$	$E_Q (cm^{-1})$	$\Gamma_Q (cm^{-1})$
4, 62	4046.243	1.151	4046.96	1.57
5, 60	3656.8474	2.120	3657.47	2.37
0, 71	6665.121	2.70	6666.14	3.24
10, 49	1931.975	3.20		
15, 37	835.21	3.30		
6, 58	3304.134	3.975		
13, 42	1218.181	4.194		
18, 29	417.77	5.08		
21, 19	105.945	5.53		
19, 26	304.154	6.23		
17, 32	564.72	7.05		
7, 56	2984.192	7.58		
1, 69	6034.261	8.062	6036.2	8.4
11, 47	1740.08	9.74		
20, 23	219.22	13.43		
8, 54	2693.27	14.60		
2, 67	5462.30	14.77	5461.5	16.0
16, 35	748.03	15.12		
3, 65	4943.45	22.49	4944.8	20.3

Table IV-1B — Resonances of $(^{40}\text{Ar-H})^+$: continuation (larger widths, up to 20 cm^{-1}).

FIGURA IV-4a

Fig. IV-4a — Top: example of resonant states, resonances of (Ne-H)⁺ with $J = 35$ in the effective potential. Bottom: bound states and the two resonances of (Ne-H)⁺ with $J = 25$ (Trial 2 potential).

Fig. IV-4b — Top: example of resonant states, resonances of $(\text{Ar-H})^+$ with $J = 62$ (Trial 2 potential). Bottom: the three resonances with $J = 32$ of $(\text{Ar-H})^+$.

graphs of the partial cross sections $\sigma_J(E)$ and the corresponding phase shifts $\delta_J(E)$ for two resonance examples taken from Tables IV:1; one can note the dis-

continuity of approximately π that appears in the phase shifts for $E \cong E_Q$. The complete set of resonances is finally represented graphically in Figure (IV-7) in the (E, J) plane.

Fig. IV-5 — Top: NeH^+ , $V=1$, $j=36$: partial cross section σ_J and phase shift δ_J ; $E_Q = 2368.23 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Gamma'_Q = 0.011 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $E_{SC} = 2367.55 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Gamma'_{SC} = 0.0097 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Bottom: NeH^+ , $V=0$, $j=39$: $E_Q = 3501.48 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $E_{SC} = 3500.97 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

FIGURA IV-6 a

Fig. IV-6a — ArH^+ , $V = 19$, $j = 25$: phase shift $\delta_J(E)$ and $|T|^2$ (top); partial cross section $\sigma_J(E)$ (bottom). $\Gamma_{SC} = 0.175 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $E_{SC}^{\text{res}} = 222.14 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

FIGURA IV-6b

Fig. IV-6b — Top: ArH^+ , $V = 2$, $j = 66$: $\sigma_J(E)$ and $\delta_J(E)$; $E_Q = 4952.176 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Gamma_Q = 0.21 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Gamma_{SC} = 0.32 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Bottom: ArH^+ , $V = 4$, $j = 61$: $E_Q = 3572.456 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Gamma_Q = 0.0069 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

FIGURA (IV-7):- LISTA COMPLETA DELLE
RISONANZE DEL $(\text{Ne-H})^+$ E DELL' $(\text{Ar-H})^+$.

-LE LINEE UNISCONO LE
RISONANZE CON LO STESSO NUMERO DI VIBRAZIONE v .

Fig. IV-7 — Complete list of resonances of $(\text{Ne-H})^+$ (top) and $(\text{Ar-H})^+$ (bottom) in the (E, J) plane. The lines connect resonances with the same vibrational quantum number v .

Chapter IV 3: Resonances and Photodissociation

§1: General Considerations

In this chapter the results of the study, carried out near the resonance energies, of the photodissociation process of the $(R-H)^+$ system with $R = Ar, Ne$, illustrated schematically in Figure (IV-8), are presented.

It should be noted that the process under consideration constitutes an example of isoelectronic predissociation, in contrast to most predissociation phenomena observed in molecular spectroscopy, which usually involve a transition from an attractive to a repulsive electronic curve either by excitation or by simple passage through the crossing point of the two electronic curves (giving rise to spontaneous predissociation). In the present case, the phenomenon instead consists of a transition from a bound state (n, J) to a continuum state (E, J') of the same ground electronic curve.

In photodissociation two probability factors enter: the probability of photon absorption, $B(n, J \rightarrow E, J')$, and the probability, determined by the mean lifetime of the quasi-bound state, that a molecular fragment is detected after a certain time t has elapsed following the transition.

* * *

§2: An experiment on discrete \rightarrow continuum transitions

Another experiment, besides that described in the preceding Chapter, carried out for the $(R-H)^+$ system with only the atom $R = He$, has measured the energy of two discrete \rightarrow continuum transitions (Carrington '81). The experiment is schematised in Figure (IV-9) and uses a beam of ionised $(He-H)^+$ molecules accelerated by electrostatic plates to a potential difference U of the order of 10 kV. The beam is purified of any other ions using a magnetic selector and then traverses a region ($d \cong 0.5$ m) in which a Laser field is present, parallel or antiparallel to the flight direction of the $(He-H)^+$ beam; any H^+ ions formed along this path by photodissociation are deflected and counted with an electron multiplier. By repeating the measurement in the absence of the laser field and using the various CO_2 laser frequencies, the ratio between the H^+ intensities measured with and

ILLUSTRAZIONE SCHEMATICA DELLA FOTODISSOCIAZIONE.

FIGURA IV - 8

Fig. IV-8 — Schematic illustration of photodissociation. Top: initial state (A-B) with incident photon $h\nu$. Middle: excitation to the quasi-bound state $(A-B)^*$ via transition $h\nu$. Bottom: dissociation into the free fragments A and B.

SHEMA DELL'ESPERIENZA SULLA FOTODISSOCIAZIONE DELL' $(\text{He-H})^+$ (CARRINGTON '81)

FIGURA IV - 9

Fig. IV-9 — Schematic of the photodissociation experiment on $(\text{He-H})^+$ (Carrington '81): magnetic selector, accelerating plates, source, deflecting plates, laser beam, detector.

without the Laser has been studied, a graph of which as a function of the laser frequency in the ion reference frame is reported in the Appendix to Chapter III.

In the case that this experiment is repeated for some other noble gas, a useful estimate of the photodissociation cross section and of the resonance energy and

width for the following reaction may be needed:

where γ is a photon of energy of the order of a thousand cm^{-1} .

* * *

§3: Dipole Moment of a Diatomic Molecule

For the calculation of the probability of reaction (IV 3.1), knowledge of the dipole moment of the molecule is indispensable (Herzberg Ch. III). The dipole moment operator of a diatomic molecule is defined by the equation:

$$\mu(r, R_1, R_2) = Z_1 e R_1 + Z_2 e R_2 - e \sum_i r_i \quad (\text{IV } 3.2)$$

If the diatomic molecule is not neutral, it depends on the choice of origin of the reference frame: a translation ΔR entails a change in the dipole of $Z\Delta R$, where Z represents the net charge of the molecule (in a.u.). Since we are dealing with ionised molecules, it is convenient to choose once and for all the origin at the nucleus of one of the two atoms, say atom 1; the first term of expression (IV 3.2) then vanishes and the second equals $Z_2 e R$ where R represents the usual internuclear distance. In the particular case of the $(\text{R-H})^+$ systems, μ can therefore be written as:

$$\mu(r, R) = eR - \mu_{el}(r). \quad (\text{IV } 3.3)$$

where $\mu_{el} = e \sum_i r_i$ represents the electronic dipole moment operator; the radial part of the expectation value of $\mu(r, R)$ between two states (N, E, J) , (N, E', J') in the same electronic state N (which is hereafter taken to be the ground state):

$$\langle N, E, J | \mu(r, R) | N, E', J' \rangle = \int d^3 R dr \Phi_N^*(r; R_1, R_2) \Psi_{EJ}^*(R) \mu(r, R) \Phi_N(r; R_1, R_2) \Psi_{E'J'}(R) \quad (\text{IV } 3.4)$$

can be written, in the Born-Oppenheimer approximation in which the wave function is $F(r, R_1, R_2) = \Phi(r; R_1, R_2) \Psi(R_1, R_2)$ (see the Introduction), as follows:

$$\langle E, J | D(R) | E', J' \rangle_N = \int dR \Psi_{EJ}^*(R) D(R) \Psi_{E'J'}(R). \quad (\text{IV } 3.5)$$

where $D(R)$, given by:

$$D(R) = \int dr \Phi_N^*(r; R_1, R_2) \mu(r, R) \Phi_N(r, R_1, R_2) \quad (\text{IV } 3.6)$$

represents the “molecular dipole moment”, depending only on the intermolecular distance R . Note that the integral in equation (IV 3.5) for the matrix element is well defined, in the sense that the integration is performed over the variable $R = |R_2 - R_1|$ and both functions on which the integral depends ($\Psi(R)$ and $D(R)$) are defined in terms of the same variable R .

For a generic diatomic molecule, the molecular dipole moment will vanish for every value of R by symmetry if the molecule is homonuclear, while it will be non-zero, in particular at the equilibrium distance R_e , if the diatomic molecule is heteronuclear, in which case it will possess a permanent dipole moment.

Imagining taking the limit $R \rightarrow 0$, in which the molecule transforms into an atom of atomic number $Z_1 + Z_2$, the dipole moment of the molecule will tend to the permanent dipole moment of the atom, which is zero. On the other hand, for $R \rightarrow \infty$, the dipole moment of a neutral molecule tends to that originating from the two separated atoms which, if the atoms are neutral, is zero. Figure (IV-10) illustrates a typical behaviour, as a function of the internuclear distance R , of the dipole moment of a neutral molecule.

The region of R over which it is necessary to know $D(R)$ is limited to the classically accessible region at the energy of the lowest bound state for which the matrix element (IV 3.5) must be calculated, outside of which the corresponding wave function, and hence also its contribution to the matrix element, is negligible. In practice it is

ESEMPIO DI DIPOLO INTERMOLECOLARE PER UNA MOLECOLA BIATOMICA NEUTRA,
(DA HERZBERG Cap. III).

FIGURA IV-10

Fig. IV-10 — Example of intermolecular dipole for a neutral diatomic molecule (from Herzberg Ch. III). The linearisation $D(R) = D_0 + D_1(R - R_e)$ around R_e is indicated.

sufficient to calculate the power series expansion in $\xi = R - R_e$ around the equilibrium point (see Figure (IV-10)) retaining only a few terms:

$$D(R) = D_0 + D_1\xi + D_2\xi^2 + \dots \quad (\text{IV } 3.7)$$

This expansion is also valid for ionised systems, whose $D(R)$ behaviour is quite different from that of neutral molecules. In our case, the dipole moment $D(R)$ of

equation (IV 3.6) can be written, taking into account equation (IV 3.3), as follows:

$$D(R) = eR - D_{el}(R) \quad (\text{IV 3.8})$$

where R represents the (positive) contribution of the proton to the dipole moment and where:

$$-D_{el}(R) = - \int dr \Phi^*(r; R_1, R_2) \sum_i er_i \Phi(r, R_1, R_2) \quad (\text{IV 3.9})$$

represents the (negative) contribution of the electron cloud of the noble gas atom, which is induced by the presence of the proton. Note that for $R \rightarrow \infty$ the wave function $\Phi(r; R_1, R_2)$ tends to the wave function $\Phi(r)$ of the isolated noble gas atom; the electron cloud is no longer appreciably polarised by the proton field and the integral in the expression for $D_{el}(R)$ tends to zero.

In the case of (R-H)⁺ systems, only ab initio calculations have so far provided an estimate of the molecular dipole moment $D(R)$ at some values of the internuclear distance.

The behaviour of the molecular dipole moment, resulting from the sum of these two contributions, is visible in Figure (IV-11) which reports the molecular dipole moment results by Rosmus (Rosmus '79, Rosmus '80): for $R \rightarrow \infty$ they are describable by the line $D(R) = R$ since at large distances the electronic contribution is negligible and it reduces to the sole contribution from the proton. It is also negligible for $R \rightarrow 0$ where, if one imagines this limit to be taken, the molecule becomes an atom with atomic number $Z_1 + 1$ and its residual dipole moment is zero.

If we subtract from the dipole moment of Figure (IV-11) the contribution of the proton ($= +eR$), and change the sign of what remains, we can isolate the electronic contribution $D_{el}(R)$, reported in Figure (IV-12). The description of the electronic part

FIGURA IV-11

Fig. IV-11 — Top: Ne-p, dipole calculated by Rosmus as a function of R (a.u.); the line $D(R) = R$ is shown for comparison. Bottom: Ar-p dipole calculated by Rosmus in the region around R_e .

FIGURA IV-12

Fig. IV-12 — Top: Ne-H⁺, dipole (electronic part) from Rosmus as a function of R (a.u.). Bottom: Ar-H⁺, dipole (electronic part) from Rosmus.

of the dipole with an analytical function is very useful for numerical calculations; not having found in the literature any particularly simple analytical function for interpolating the dipole functions of Figure (IV-12), the following functions were

used:

$$f_1(R) = f_0 R^\alpha \exp(-\beta R) \quad (\text{for Ar-H}^+) \quad (\text{IV 3.10a})$$

$$f_2(R) = f_0 R^\alpha \exp(-\beta R^2) \quad (\text{for Ne-H}^+) \quad (\text{IV 3.10b})$$

The parameters of this function were found using an optimisation program, written specifically for the purpose, that minimises the mean deviation between the values to be reproduced, calculated by Rosmus, and the values obtained through functions (IV 3.10). The optimisation method used by the program (see the Appendix to Chapter IV) is the simple gradient method, which reaches the optimal values of the parameters by continuously comparing the value of the deviation calculated for certain parameters with that obtained for slightly different parameters. In Figure (IV-13) the comparison between the data points to be interpolated and the corresponding analytical function is shown. Below is instead reported the direct comparison together with the respective percentage errors (all in a.u.):

Table IV.2 — Interpolation parameters for the molecular dipole

(Ne-H) ⁺			
$f_0 = 0.5186617 \quad \alpha = 1.216458 \quad \beta = 0.1504574$			
X (a.u.)	YFIT	Y	DY(%)
1.0000	0.446212	0.442300	0.8845
1.0500	0.466251	0.464300	0.4202
1.1000	0.485481	0.485200	0.0578
1.2000	0.521328	0.523000	0.3197
1.3000	0.553429	0.555900	0.4445
1.5000	0.605439	0.607500	0.3393
1.7000	0.640287	0.640900	0.0956
1.9000	0.657792	0.657400	0.0596
2.1000	0.658701	0.658100	0.0914
2.3000	0.644536	0.644300	0.0367

FIGURA IV-13

Fig. IV-13 — Top: NeH^+ , interpolation function for the Rosmus dipole as a function of R (a.u.), with the original data points. Bottom: ArH^+ , interpolation function for the Rosmus dipole.

Table IV.2 (continued) — Parameters for (Ne-H)⁺ (large R values) and (Ar-H)⁺

(Ne-H) ⁺ (continued)			
X	YFIT	Y	DY(%)
2.5000	0.617403	0.617400	0.0005
2.7000	0.579790	0.579400	0.0673
2.9000	0.534366	0.532800	0.2939
3.1000	0.483794	0.480800	0.6227
3.3000	0.430577	0.426700	0.9087
3.5000	0.376938	0.373600	0.8936
4.0000	0.252220	0.259500	2.8054
6.0000	0.020376	0.079100	74.2395
9.0000	0.000038	0.032000	99.8804
15.0000	0.27D-13	0.011600	100.0000

(Ar-H) ⁺ : $f_0 = 1.181748$, $\alpha = 1.481420$, $\beta = 0.4367958$			
X	YFIT	Y	DY(%)
1.9000	1.33367	1.33450	0.0619
2.1000	1.41743	1.41770	0.0192
2.2000	1.45365	1.45360	0.0037
2.3500	1.50121	1.50080	0.0274
2.5000	1.54098	1.5405	0.0310
2.7000	1.58260	1.58260	0.0000
3.0000	1.62274	1.62370	0.0594
3.3000	1.63930	1.63930	0.0000

These functions can be used directly in the calculation of the dipole matrix elements, or can be used to calculate the first derivatives of $D(R)$ at $R = R_e$.

It can be noted that while the agreement is good for values of R not too large, the functions used are unable to describe the dipole behaviour for R greater than about 4 a.u.; indeed the dipole does not decrease exponentially but reduces, for large R , to the moment induced by the proton which, if E_p here represents the electrostatic field generated by the proton, equals:

$$D^\infty(R) = -\alpha E_p = -\alpha e/R^2, \quad (\text{IV } 3.11)$$

where α is the atomic polarisability of the noble gas atom; the dipole therefore decreases with the inverse square of the distance. We shall therefore take as the dipole function one of expressions (IV 3.10) for R not too large, while for large distances it is possible to use, as suggested by expression (IV 3.11), a power series in the inverse of the distance.

§4: Photodissociation Cross Sections

The cross sections for photodissociation occurring via a transition from a bound state (n, J) to a continuum state (E, J') will be studied here through the formula:

$$\sigma_{PH}(n, J \rightarrow E, J') = 8\pi^3 \alpha \hbar \omega |\langle eJ | D(\text{a.u.}) | n, J' \rangle|^2 \quad (\text{IV 3.12})$$

where α is the fine structure constant and $D(\text{a.u.}) = D(R)/e$ is the molecular dipole moment measured in atomic units. The mathematical tools employed in the calculation of the dipole matrix element have already been described; its calculation requires knowledge of the molecular dipole function, treated in §3 of the present chapter, and of the two wave functions of the bound state and the continuum state, which are calculated by the programs discussed in Chapters II 1 and II 2. The dipole matrix element is then calculated by numerical integration for those transitions permitted by the angular momentum selection rules, $\Delta J = \pm 1$, and the vibrational selection rule, $\Delta n = \pm 1$, valid in practice also for discrete \rightarrow continuum transitions. Since the vibrational energy is much greater than the rotational energy, the only selection rules that are in practice realised for discrete-continuum transitions are $\Delta n = +1$ and $\Delta J = \pm 1$; taking these rules into account, it is possible to establish readily, from Figure (IV-7), the full set of possible discrete \rightarrow continuum transitions, which we report in Tables IV.3a and IV.3b, and which can be used together with Tables IV.1a and IV.1b to identify the laser absorption lines in possible experiments, of the type described at the beginning of the present Chapter, for Ne-H^+ or $(\text{Ar-H})^+$.

Expression (IV 3.12) has been studied in the energy regions around the resonance energies of the final states. The initial estimate of the resonance positions was taken from Tables IV.1 and proved to be very close to that of photodissociation where σ_{PH} exhibited a typical resonant “bell-shaped” behaviour. This behaviour can be seen in Figures IV.14, which report the comparison between the behaviour of the scattering cross sections and the photodissociation cross sections in the vicinity of the resonance energies. Only two examples are reported for the “Trial 2” potential, one for Ar-H^+ and one for Ne-H^+ , and some examples calculated with the GT potential, confirming the equivalence of the resonance definitions through $\sigma_{PH}(E)$ and through $\sigma_J(E)$. It can further be noted that, unlike the photodissociation cross sections, the scattering cross sections do not necessarily exhibit a maximum but may also present a minimum, due in any case to the rapid variation of the phase shift $\delta_J(E)$ near the resonance energy.

* * *

The results of the theory of the directional photoelectric effect were then used,

which describes the angular distribution of the electron emitted from an atom with a single electron, using the formula for the differential photodissociation cross section:

$$d\sigma/d\Omega = (1/4\pi)\sigma_{PH}(E)(1 + \beta(E) \times P_2 \cos \Theta) \quad (\text{IV 3.14})$$

where P_2 is the second Legendre polynomial and $\beta(E)$ can be expressed in terms of the dipole matrix element (see Berkowitz Ch. , Cooper '69). Indeed, although the physical system is quite different, the mechanism (dissociation of the electron from the atom following the absorption of a photon) is the same, and so are the calculations of the photodissociation probability.

The result has been that for several resonances, of which we report an example in Figure (IV-16), a sudden transition to a highly anisotropic fragment distribution occurs in the vicinity of the resonance energy, which should be experimentally detectable, even if perhaps more difficult to observe than a photoelectron.

$(n, J) \rightarrow (n', J')$	$\Delta E (\text{cm}^{-1})$	$\Gamma_{n', J'} (\text{cm}^{-1})$			
$(1, 30) \rightarrow (2, 31)$	1889.06	$8.86 \cdot 10^{-24}$	$(0, 34) \rightarrow (1, 35)$	1853.711	$3.07 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$(1, 32) \rightarrow (2, 31)$	2521.419	$8.86 \cdot 10^{-24}$	$(6, 20) \rightarrow (7, 21)$	941.4113	$8.76 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$(0, 32) \rightarrow (1, 33)$	2080.952	$1.94 \cdot 10^{-23}$	$(1, 32) \rightarrow (2, 33)$	1671.039	$1.43 \cdot 10^{-5}$
$(0, 34) \rightarrow (1, 33)$	552.0402	"	$(2, 30) \rightarrow (3, 31)$	1489.677	$1.07 \cdot 10^{-4}$
$(2, 28) \rightarrow (3, 29)$	3761.807	$4.35 \cdot 10^{-23}$	$(5, 23) \rightarrow (6, 24)$	1046.8822	$3.7 \cdot 10^{-41}$
$(2, 30) \rightarrow (3, 29)$	2572.997	"			
$(3, 26) \rightarrow (4, 27)$	1503.37	$9.26 \cdot 10^{-21}$	$(3, 28) \rightarrow (4, 29)$	1309.515	$1.167 \cdot 10^{-3}$
$(3, 28) \rightarrow (4, 27)$	471.0075	"	$(11, 6) \rightarrow (12, 7)$	170.6933	0.02834
$(4, 24) \rightarrow (5, 25)$	1314.238	$9.13 \cdot 10^{-17}$	$(11, 8) \rightarrow (12, 7)$	71.9738	0.02834
$(4, 26) \rightarrow (5, 25)$	429.57	"	$(4, 26) \rightarrow (5, 27)$	1129.461	0.01915
$(8, 14) \rightarrow (9, 15)$	716.653	$4.18 \cdot 10^{-15}$	$(7, 18) \rightarrow (8, 19)$	757.3293	0.0910
$(8, 16) \rightarrow (9, 15)$	340.960	"	$(7, 20) \rightarrow (8, 19)$	263.691	0.0910
$(10, 8) \rightarrow (11, 9)$	411.205	$4.28 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$(6, 21) \rightarrow (7, 22)$	864.65	0.1179
$(10, 10) \rightarrow (11, 9)$	239.136	"	$(8, 15) \rightarrow (9, 16)$	633.03	0.48285
$(5, 22) \rightarrow (6, 23)$	1323.972	$8.09 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$(8, 17) \rightarrow (9, 16)$	251.785	0.48285
$(5, 24) \rightarrow (6, 23)$	381.430	"	$(5, 24) \rightarrow (6, 25)$	949.255	0.4571
$(0, 33) \rightarrow (1, 34)$	1974.018	$8.91 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$(12, 4) \rightarrow (13, 5)$	58.40	0.80215
$(1, 31) \rightarrow (2, 32)$	1785.976	$5.48 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$(12, 6) \rightarrow (13, 5)$	20.677	0.80215
$(7, 17) \rightarrow (8, 18)$	818.1861	$1.59 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$(10, 9) \rightarrow (11, 10)$	335.89	2.547
$(7, 19) \rightarrow (8, 18)$	325.670	"	$(10, 11) \rightarrow (11, 10)$	154.43	2.547
$(9, 11) \rightarrow (10, 12)$	889.595	$2.95 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$(9, 12) \rightarrow (10, 13)$	494.4	4.9667
$(9, 13) \rightarrow (10, 12)$	621.8026	"	$(9, 14) \rightarrow (10, 13)$	218.3	4.9667
$(2, 29) \rightarrow (3, 30)$	1599.121	$7.22 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$(6, 22) \rightarrow (7, 23)$	766.7	3.160
$(3, 27) \rightarrow (4, 28)$	1413.656	$2.41 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$(7, 19) \rightarrow (8, 20)$	680.5	11.42
$(4, 25) \rightarrow (5, 26)$	1229.658	$1.95 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$(8, 16) \rightarrow (9, 17)$	570.8	20.41

TABELLA IV-3A

 TRANSIZIONI DISCRETO \rightarrow CONTINUO del $({}^{20}\text{Ne-H})^+$

 Table IV-3A — Discrete \rightarrow continuum transitions of $({}^{20}\text{Ne-H})^+$: initial and final states $(n, J) \rightarrow (n', J')$, energy ΔE (cm^{-1}) and width $\Gamma_{n', J'}$ (cm^{-1}).

$(n, J) \rightarrow (n', J')$	$\Delta E (\text{cm}^{-1})$	$\Gamma_{n'J'} (\text{cm}^{-1})$
$(12, 39) \rightarrow (13, 40)$	799.20936	1.835×10^{-5}
$(14, 34) \rightarrow (15, 35)$	664.25564	2.199×10^{-5}
$(23, 8) \rightarrow (24, 9)$	47.67286	3.283×10^{-5}
$(23, 10) \rightarrow (24, 9)$	15.84902	"
$(18, 23) \rightarrow (19, 24)$	392.60708	3.329×10^{-5}
$(18, 25) \rightarrow (19, 24)$	140.3233	"
$(17, 26) \rightarrow (18, 27)$	457.8638	7.698×10^{-5}
$(19, 20) \rightarrow (20, 21)$	322.9459	0.000105
$(19, 22) \rightarrow (20, 21)$	119.97398	"
$(16, 29) \rightarrow (17, 30)$	516.8652	0.00046
$(15, 32) \rightarrow (16, 33)$	567.9376	0.0037
$(20, 17) \rightarrow (21, 18)$	249.4334	0.00581
$(20, 19) \rightarrow (21, 18)$	93.4573	"
$(24, 6) \rightarrow (25, 7)$	22.527	0.02514
$(24, 8) \rightarrow (25, 7)$	5.637	"
$(22, 11) \rightarrow (23, 12)$	87.178	0.0498
$(22, 13) \rightarrow (23, 12)$	21.89	"
$(17, 27) \rightarrow (18, 28)$	415.665	0.145
$(18, 24) \rightarrow (19, 25)$	356.510	0.195
$(16, 30) \rightarrow (17, 31)$	467.60	0.259
$(21, 14) \rightarrow (22, 15)$	167.52	0.277
$(21, 16) \rightarrow (22, 15)$	233.27	"
$(19, 21) \rightarrow (20, 22)$	291.551	0.625
$(20, 18) \rightarrow (21, 19)$	219.4147	5.53
$(18, 25) \rightarrow (19, 26)$	312.73	6.23
$(19, 22) \rightarrow (20, 23)$	254.52	13.43

TABELLA IV-3B : TRANSIZIONI
DISCRETO \rightarrow CONTINUO DELL' $({}^{40}\text{Ar-H})^+$

Table IV-3B — Discrete \rightarrow continuum transitions of $({}^{40}\text{Ar-H})^+$: initial and final states $(n, J) \rightarrow (n', J')$, energy $\Delta E (\text{cm}^{-1})$ and width $\Gamma_{n'J'} (\text{cm}^{-1})$.

Fig. (IV-14)a — Top: $\text{NeH}^+, V = 2, j = 33 \leftarrow V = 1, j = 32$: $\sigma_{PH}(E)$; $E_{PH} = 1450.646872 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Gamma_{PH} = 0.14 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Bottom: partial cross section σ_J and phase shift; $E_Q = 1450.646822 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Gamma_Q = 0.24 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Fig. (IV-14)b — Top: Ar-H⁺, dissociative transition $v = 15, J = 32 \Rightarrow v = 16, J = 33$: $\sigma_{PH}(E)$; $E_{PH} = 474.861$, $\Gamma_{PH} = 0.0029$. Bottom: orbiting resonance $v = 16, J = 33$: $\sigma_J(E)$ and $\delta_J(E)$; $E_Q = 474.8540$, $\Gamma_Q = 0.0030$.

FIGURA (IV-15)_a

Fig. (IV-15)a — Top: Ar-H^+ , transition $V = 14, J = 31 \implies V = 15, J = 32$, $\sigma_{PH}(E)$.
 Bottom: $v = 15, j = 32$, GT parameters, $\sigma_J(E)$ and $\delta_J(E)$; $E_{s.c.} = 456.873682$,
 $\Gamma_{s.c.} = 0.000352$, $E_Q = 457.32725$, $\Gamma_Q = 0.0005$.

 FIGURA (IV-15)_b

Fig. (IV-15)_b — Top: Ar-H^+ , transition $v = 11, j = 39 \Rightarrow v = 12, j = 40$, $\sigma_{PH}(E)$. Bottom: $v = 12, j = 40$, GT parameters, $\sigma_J(E)$; $E_{s.c.} = 901.196059 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Gamma_{s.c.} = 0.0000167 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $E_Q = 901.788492 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Gamma_Q = 0.000024 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

FIGURA (IV-15)_c

Fig. (IV-15)c — Top: transition $v = 14, j = 32 \Rightarrow v = 15, j = 33$, $\sigma_{PH}(E)$ and $\beta(E)$. Bottom: $v = 15, J = 33$, GT parameters, $\sigma_J(E)$; $E_{s.c.} = 631.675 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Gamma_{s.c.} = 0.234 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $E_a = 632.038 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Gamma_a = 0.278 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

FIGURA (IV-15)d

Fig. (IV-15)d — Top: transition $v = 16, j = 25 \Rightarrow v = 17, j = 26$, $\sigma_{PH}(E)$.
 Bottom: Ar..H⁺, $v = 17, j = 26$, G.T. parameters, $\sigma_J(E)$; $E_{s.c.} = 231.2477 \text{ cm}^{-1}$,
 $\Gamma_{s.c.} = 0.0016 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $E_a = 231.6015 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Gamma_a = 0.0017 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Fig. IV-16 — (Ne-H)⁺, discrete→continuum transition (V = 4, J = 26) → (V = 5, J = 27). Left: $\sigma_{PH}(E)$ and $\beta(E)$ (photodissociation); $E_{PH} = 894.4818 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Gamma_{PH} = 0.0198 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Top right: scattering resonance (V = 5, J = 26), $\sigma_J(E)$ and $\delta_J(E)$ (semiclassical method); $E_{s.c.} = 894.1140$, $\Gamma_{s.c.} = 0.0132$. Bottom right: predissociation; $E_Q = 894.483$, $\Gamma_Q = 0.0204$.

IV-4 Conclusions

The study carried out on the resonant states and summarised in Tables IV.1 and in Figures (IV-5) and (IV-6) immediately leads to a first general conclusion about the different definitions of resonance. The equivalence of the definition through the time delay function with the quantum definition that studies the partial cross section σ_J has already been extensively discussed (Le Roy '71). The calculations performed in this work represent a verification (see Le Roy '78) that the semiclassical Airy function boundary-condition method gives results consistent, for the resonance energies and widths, with the quantum method that uses the σ_J (see Tables IV.1).

Furthermore, the study of the photodissociation cross section (see the various graphs comparing the σ_J with the σ_{PH} near the resonance energies) has demonstrated the equivalence of the previous definitions with the "spectroscopic" definition of resonance; it should be noted that this is not equivalence with a semiclassical definition such as that using the "inner amplitude function" $A_J(E)$, but equivalence with a purely quantum definition defined through the σ_{PH} . The conclusion follows that photodissociation resonances are to be sought in the energy regions where scattering resonances appear.

Furthermore, a theoretical study of the resonances of $(\text{Ar-H})^+$ and $(\text{Ne-H})^+$ had not been available until now, while $(\text{He-H})^+$ had been extensively studied (see Peek '73 for the theoretical study of resonances, Atabek '85 A,B for the theoretical study of photodissociation of He-H^+), which, being a diatomic system with only two electrons, had allowed accurate ab initio calculations.

Regarding the energy and width of the resonances, it should be said that although the use of the different potentials considered led to some differences, the resonances were nevertheless always identified by the same vibrational and rotational quantum numbers n and J . The error on their energy, of the order of a tenth of a percent for the lowest bound states as reported by the Trial 2 potential, must certainly be considered larger (of the order of a percent) for the resonances; it must further be borne in mind that a small error in the resonance energies can lead to larger errors in their mean lifetimes. Tables IV.1 may nonetheless prove useful should the experiment described in Chapter IV 2 be extended to other noble gases.

The same can be said for Tables IV.3, which report the discrete \rightarrow continuum transitions for $(\text{Ne-H})^+$ and $(\text{Ar-H})^+$ for experiments similar to those described in Chapter IV 3 but performed with Ne or Ar atoms, in which they can be used to identify and assign the correct quantum numbers to the detected absorption lines.

Appendix IV: Optimisation Program for the Dipole Function

The optimisation program that was used to find an analytical form for the dipole functions is essentially an optimisation program.

It minimises a suitably defined root-mean-square deviation, representing the goodness of the parameters of the analytical function used for interpolating the known data points; the best parameters are taken as those that minimise this mean deviation. The program has proved useful in other circumstances, such as in the search for an analytical function passing through the few data points of the Rosmus potential or for verifying the correctness of the molecular constants used.

To illustrate the calculation method, let us fix ideas with a function of parameters a, b with which one wishes to interpolate known data points: one must find the point, in the a - b plane, where the deviation function reaches a minimum. The method used is that of the gradient; the program starts from an initial point a_o, b_o where it calculates the deviation to be minimised in the a - b plane; it then compares this with neighbouring points until it finds one where the deviation appears to decrease, and takes as the new parameters those corresponding to the point found. Once the new parameters have been found, the procedure is repeated at the new point, until the minimum of the deviation is found.

In one dimension (for a single parameter) it is sufficient to increase or decrease that single parameter until the minimum of the deviation is found. In more dimensions the variations cannot be carried out by varying one parameter at a time, but it is necessary to vary all parameters simultaneously; geometrically, this means that to find the minimum in the a - b plane, it is not sufficient to move in directions parallel to the X or Y axis, but one must be able to take any direction, otherwise one risks becoming trapped at a point far from the minimum simply because the direction in which the deviation decreases is not parallel to one of the axes. The program therefore carries out the variations by moving in the “parameter space” and trying all directions; the method used to explore the various directions does not follow “random” criteria or other particular criteria, but systematically scans the various directions; for this reason the number of parameters that can be varied is not, for reasons of computation time, greater than 4.

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